

Deliverable D4.1

Inventory of currently available standards/guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics

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1. Introduction

Aim of MICROBE

The project MICROBE aims

- to deliver innovative validated technological approaches for optimal collection and preservation of microbiome samples (maintaining their taxonomic and functional biodiversity), as well as for the targeted isolation of microbiome members and assembly of synthetic consortia;
- and to provide a comprehensive operational blueprint for the establishment of microbiome biobanking infrastructure, including technological requirements, methodological workflows, data pipelines, legal and ethical guidelines, training plans and business opportunities.

MICROBE will also address the important issues related to standardization and quality control (QC) by developing guidelines for the implementation of standardized workflows and validating developed workflows in ring trials.

Microbiome research field, standardization and sample pre-analytics

The microbiome research field is a fast-evolving area with currently only a few widely accepted quality standards. In comparison to industry, standards are generally not yet well established in research communities. However, this rapid development and the growing spectrum of analytical technologies have raised awareness of the importance of quality controls and standardization in microbiome research. Particularly for biobanks (including microbiome biobanks) acting at the interface between research and industry and aiming to provide access to samples and data of a high and defined quality, it is crucial to follow standards relevant to the industry. This also applies to research projects that focus on the development of novel applications and technologies. The European Commission recently published the COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2023/498 that advised applying ISO and/or CEN standards also for research, particularly for EU projects and ‘to make standards a tangible component of the project. (European Commission, 2023).

Along the entire microbiome (analytical) workflow (pre-analytical, analytical and post-analytical phase) numerous factors can artificially modify the final analytical result.

The pre-analytical phase (figure 1) has been shown to be a main, but still often underestimated, contributor to inaccurate or even false and irreproducible analysis. This phase consists of several critical steps with multiple factors that can have a severe impact on the analysis result and research outcome. It ranges from sample donor/site, sample collection, preservation (stabilization), transport, processing, storage and often also DNA or RNA isolation, measurement and storage (Figure 1). Several of these steps or processes do not lie within one hand (e.g. the biobank’s hand) but are performed by multiple involved parties. This increases the need for a coordinated and standardized process.

Figure 1: Pre-analytical phase of a typical microbiome (DNA/RNA) analysis

During the past years international and European standards have been developed.

The term 'standards' used in this deliverable report (and in the entire WP4 of MICROBE) refers to internal ISO and European CEN standards which are written documents. It does not refer to 'standards' in terms of 'reference material', which is a material used to check the quality and metrological traceability of products, validate analytical methods or for calibration of analytical instruments.

The ISO and CEN standards developed in recent years include, for example, standards for “biobanking” and standards for (pre-analytical) sample quality. One of these (pre-analytical) sample quality standards is **CEN/TS 17626:2021 for human specimens intended for microbiome analysis** (*Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations. Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimen. Isolated microbiome DNA*). As the human microbiome research field is more advanced, it will serve as an example of best practices for other fields and the existing European standard CEN/TS 17626:2021 as a template for the development of pre-analytical phase guidance documents for other sample types.

In addition to international ISO and pan-European CEN standards, also several specialist groups, initiatives, consortia, or organizations have written guidelines or best practices documents for their communities.

Description of Deliverable D4.1 & objective of Task T4.1

This deliverable report (D4.1 “Inventory of currently available standards/guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics”) provides an inventory of pan-European and international standards, guidelines or best practices that exist or are under development for pre-analytical workflows for various types of microbiome samples.

D4.1 belongs to Work Package WP4 “Standardization and Quality Control (QC)” and is the result of the Task T4.1 “Inventory of standards/guidelines/best practices”. The aim of T4.1 was to perform a mapping of pan-European and international standards/guidelines/best practices that exist or are under development for pre-analytical workflows for various types of microbiome samples.

Within this report, the major focus lays on pan-European and international standards and guidelines/best practices that address the pre-analytical phase (and pre-analytical factors) of microbiome-containing samples that are intended for microbiome analysis. The mapping effort focused on the sample types that were defined as use cases in the MICROBE proposal and are at the core of MICROBE’s research activities (i.e. **human, soil, marine water and seed microbiome-containing samples**).

Note that standards/guidelines/best practices for microbiome analyses such as microbiome phenotyping, genomics (16S rRNA, 18S rRNA, ITS amplicon sequencing, metagenomics), metatranscriptomics (e.g. RNA-based sequencing, massive parallel sequencing), metabolomics (e.g. LC/QC-MS), metaproteomics (e.g. LC/QC-MS) and cultivation, were not in the focus of this report.

2. Method

For creating the ‘inventory of standards, /guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics’, MUG performed a desktop search as described below.

- a. For international and pan-European (ISO and CEN) quality standards, MUG searched the ISO¹ and CEN² portals using a full-text search with the search term with additional filters like “Active/Preliminary/Published”, and select “Current stage”. The main search terms were “microbiome”, “microb*”, “soil”, “plant”, “seed”, “marine”, “samples”, “microorg*”, “biobanking”, “virus”, “fungi”, “and “data”);
- b. For guidelines/best practices from microbiome and biobanking initiatives, consortia, or organizations, MUG searched on the internet and/or on websites of such initiatives, consortia, or organizations;

MUG also investigated documents and links provided by MICROBE partners (*AIT, CABI, INRAE, HMGU, EMBL, SU*).

MUG performed the search between March and June 2023 with a focus put on the relevance for the MICROBE project (as described above). The inventory is, therefore, not a complete list of all existing and searched standards/guidelines/best practices.

The mapping was performed in two rounds. In the first round, MUG screened the title of the documents and excluded obviously non-relevant documents (e.g. standards for industries other than life sciences that appeared in the keyword searches). In the second round, MUG further analyzed the remaining potentially relevant documents by reading into document parts such as the introduction, scope and table of contents. Where available and needed, the entire documents were screened to assess their relevance for the inventory.

Criteria for defining the relevance were: i) the extent to which they address pre-analytical phase (e.g. number of and/or grade of details about pre-analytical steps and pre-analytical factors), ii) the referring to microbiome and/or the purpose for microbiome analysis (no other or single microorganism analysis), as well as iii) the referring to sample types human, soil, marine water, and seeds, which were defined by MICROBE as candidates for the case studies. Note: ISO and CEN standards are not freely available as full documents but need to be purchased. MUG, however, has access to draft versions of standards from certain Technical Committees (TCs) where it acts as ISO/CEN representative. Such standards could be inspected

¹ ISO portal, <https://login.iso.org/portal/>

² CEN portal, <https://projex.cencenelec.eu>

in more detail than other standards, where only limited details are accessible free of charge (typically the title, scope, and table of content).

Standards under development are included in the inventory as far as detailed information was available. These new standards will be further monitored in *T4.3 Exchange with European and international standardization bodies CEN and ISO*. MUG and HMGU are participants in certain Technical Committees at ISO and CEN (e.g. ISO/TC190, ISO/TC276, ISO/TC212, and CEN/TC140). In this role, they (particularly MUG) will attend ISO and CEN TC working groups and plenary meetings and observe the development of the standard landscape that is relevant for microbiome biobanking research infrastructures. They will inform the MICROBE consortium about relevant existing and upcoming microbiome-related standards.

Note: Not considered in the mapping were local/national standards, standards that are not valid any more (because they were replaced by newer ones), publications by researchers giving recommendations, or documents addressing the analytical phase of microbiome investigations.

This report describes the mapping results and presents the inventory also in the form of tables and matrices in the next chapters.

3. Results

3.1 International and pan-European (ISO and CEN) quality standards for microbiome sample pre-analytics

About ISO and CEN standards

ISO and CEN standards are technical documents established by consensus and approved by the recognized body (i.e. ISO or CEN). They contain rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results and define requirements for products, processes and/or services to meet fitness-for-purpose. Standards are generated in ISO or CEN Technical Committees by experts from ISO or CEN member states and conceived by an agreement (i.e. consensus) among them. Consensus means that the involved parties agree on the content (particularly the scope and the requirements and recommendations) and that there are no sustained oppositions. The core objective of consensus is to take into account the views of all interested parties and to eliminate any counterarguments.

ISO and CEN standards are based on scientific literature and on experts' experiences (evidence-based). Numerous experts from the member states contribute to the standard development in meetings and commenting rounds (i.e. ballots). Therefore, ISO and CEN standards are the result of extensive efforts and are (with only minor exceptions) not available free of charge. They can be purchased for a reasonable fee, e.g. at the international, European or national standardization bodies. All standardization documents are protected by copyright and associated exploitation rights (CEN-CENELEC (FAQs), 2023).

The development process of standards comprises several phases and takes several years. At ISO, it starts with a ‘new work item proposal’ (NWIP), which can be submitted, e.g. by an ISO member, ISO working body, or an organization in liaison with ISO. At CEN, work begins with a proposal for a standard, which can come from, e.g. member of CEN, the European Commission or an organization (CEN-CENELEC (Internal Regulations), 2023; ISO/IEC (Directives), 2023).

There are different types of standard documents which are being developed on international and/or European level. (ISO (Deliverables), 2016; CEN (Deliverables), 2016)) (Table 1).

Table 1: Standard documents are being developed at international and/or European level

Developed at International Level	Developed at European Level
ISO Standard (ISO)	European Standard (EN)
Technical Specifications (ISO/TS)	Technical Specification (CEN/TS)
Technical Report (ISO/TR)	Technical Report (CEN/TR)
Publicly Available Specification (ISO/PAS)	CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)
International Workshop Agreement (IWA)	Guide (CEN Guide).

CEN and ISO have an agreement on technical cooperation called the ‘Vienna Agreement’, which aims to prevent duplication of effort and reduce the time invested in preparing standards. The Vienna Agreement ensures that the standards for the European internal market would not be developed in isolation from international standardization. (CEN (Vienna Agreement), 2016, CEN (Guidelines) 2016).

Under the Vienna Agreement, European CEN standards that are of global relevance are taken up at ISO for the development of international ISO standards, which will then replace the former CEN standards. This is the case with the published European standard CEN/TS 17626, which is currently developed under the Vienna Agreement to the international ISO standard ISO/TS 18701.

Standardization organizations also exist on a national level. These include National Standardization Bodies, such as DIN³ (in Germany), AFNOR⁴ (in France), Austrian Standards ASI⁵ (in Austria), or BSI⁶ (in the UK). They work together under the roof of the aforementioned European and international standardization bodies and send representatives to respective Technical Committees. **The focus of this report lies on international (ISO) and European (CEN) and not on national standards from the national standardization bodies.**

Standards must not be mistaken for standard operating procedures (SOPs), laboratory protocols or best practices, because they differ widely in intent and specificity. ISO and CEN quality standards are lists of requirements and recommendations that shall (i.e. must) or should (strongly advised) be met in order to ensure quality practice. These standards do not contain explanations on how to implement the requirements and recommendations in order to comply with them. They are not as detailed as SOPs and laboratory protocols, which are developed by and specific to a certain laboratory (for comparison, see Stumptner et al., 2021). However, **standards provide the basis for SOPs and laboratory protocols.** SOPs and laboratory

³ DIN, <https://www.din.de/en>

⁴ AFNOR, <https://www.afnor.org/en/purchase-a-standard/>

⁵ Austrian Standards ASI, <https://www.austrian-standards.at/>

⁶ BSI, <https://www.bsigroup.com/>

protocols should address in their step-by-step instructions also those steps and actions needed to fulfil the standards' requirements and recommendations.

Standards are per se not mandatory, but considered as state-of-the-art, for example, in regulations. One of these regulations is the EU In-vitro Diagnostics Regulation 2017/746 (IVDR)⁷, where adherence to standards is needed to comply with this regulation (Dagher et al., 2019). In addition, standards are relevant for organizations that decide to be/become certified and accredited to a certain standard. Conforming to ISO or CEN standards is **a pre-requisite for receiving the certification from accreditation or certification bodies** and is assessed by auditors in quality audits.

Inventory of relevant ISO and CEN standards

The computerized search in the ISO and CEN portals yielded results shown in Table 2.

In two rounds of selection and evaluation (see chapter methods), standards highly relevant for MICROBE were identified. Primarily, WP4-relevant standards were identified as they can serve as a template and source of information for T4.2 "*Development of a guidance document for sample pre-analytics*". In addition, this report includes standards that are interesting for other MICROBE WPs (even if they do not cover the pre-analytical phase in detail).

While the ISO portal allows a keyword search in the title, the CEN portal allows a full-text search in the title and in the entire document. Therefore, higher numbers of hits were obtained for CEN standards. The CEN portal does not only list CEN standards but also ISO standards (termed "CEN ISO" standards (see Table 2, numbers in brackets).

⁷ IVDR, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/746/oj>

Table 2: Figures from search for ISO and CEN standards

ISO				CEN		
https://login.iso.org/portal/				https://projex.cencenelec.eu		
hits (all)	hits (related to topic) ¹	hits (highly relevant) ²	Keywords used for search	hits (all)	hits (related to topic) ¹	hits (highly relevant) ²
1	1	1	Microbiome³	7 (4)	1	1
220	151	4	microb	264 (87)	19	2
301	69	10	soil	434 (226)	33	0
500	6	1	marine	166 (54)	0	0
13	13	0	seeds	33 (10)	0	0
104	1	0	sample	1087 (529)	0	0
17	7	6	biobanking	0	0	0
17	9	5	biobank*	0	1	1
2001	6	5	data	1431 (833)	0	0
2	1	0	fungi	56 (41)	0	0
5	5	0	virus	34	0	0
35	3	1	microorg	139 (67)	0	0

Legend: ¹ = outcome of first round of selection based on titles, i.e. standards related to the topic, include therefore standards with high, medium, and low relevance; ² = outcome of second round of selection based on titles plus scope, introduction, and table of contents), i.e. standards of high relevance; ^{1,2} = relevance evaluated based on publicly available; ³ = listed in Table 3 under human; figures in brackets = numbers of CEN standards adjusted for ISO standards (i.e. after removal of “CEN ISO” standards)

Identified (highly) relevant ISO and CEN standards were/are generated in different Technical Committees:

- CEN/TC 140, In vitro diagnostic medical devices
- ISO/TC 212, Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems
- ISO/TC 276, Biotechnology
- ISO/TC 215, Health informatics
- CEN/TC 455 Plant biostimulants and agricultural micro-organisms

These Technical Committees are potential candidates for MICROBE to apply for a liaison, which is one of the aims of T4.3 “Exchange with European and intern. standard bodies CEN and ISO”.

Table 3 gives an overview of the ISO and CEN standards identified as relevant. It comprises standards for sample types defined as use cases in MICROBE. It also comprises standards for “biobanking”, “data” and “analysis”, which contain information on microbiome sample pre-analytics.

Table 3: International and pan-European (ISO and CEN) quality standards for microbiome sample pre-analytics with (high) relevance

ISO or CEN Standard Number & Title	Link	Content Addressed				
		Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data Issues	Ethics /Legal Issues	Other Bio-bank Issues
Human (ISO/TC 212 Clinical laboratory testing & in vitro diagnostic test systems WG4 Microbiology & molecular diagnostics)						
- ISO/AWI TS 18701 Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
Human (CEN/TC 140 In vitro diagnostic systems WG3 Quality management in the medical laboratory)						
- CEN/TS 17626:2021 Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations - Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimen - Isolated microbiome DNA	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
Soil (ISO/TC 190 Soil quality)						
- ISO 11063:2020 Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
- ISO 15903:2002 Soil quality — Format for recording soil and site information	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- ISO 18400-101:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 101: Framework for the preparation and application of a sampling plan	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- ISO 18400-102:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 102: Selection and application of sampling techniques	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
- ISO 18400-105:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
- ISO/AWI 18400-105 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
- ISO 18400-206:2018 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 206: Collection, handling and storage of soil under aerobic conditions for the assessment of microbiological processes, biomass and diversity in the laboratory	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
- ISO 18512:2007 Soil quality — Guidance on long and short term storage of soil samples	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- ISO 18400-107:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 107: Recording and reporting	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- ISO 18400-106:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 106: Quality control and quality assurance	Link	✓	-	-	-	-
Plant (CEN/TC 455/WG 3)						
- CEN/TS 17708:2022 Plant biostimulants - Preparation of sample for microbial analysis	Link	✓	✓	-	-	-

ISO or CEN Standard Number & Title	Link	Content Addressed				
		Pre-analyt-ics & QM	Ana-lysis	Data Issues	Ethics /Legal Issues	Other Bio-bank Issues
Biobanking (ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology)						
- <u>ISO 20387:2018</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking — General requirements for biobanking	Link	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- <u>ISO/TR 22758:2020</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking — Implementation guide for ISO 20387	Link	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- <u>ISO 21899:2020</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking — General requirements for the validation and verification of processing methods for biological material in biobanks	Link	✓				
- <u>ISO/TS 23105:2021</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for the biobanking of plant biological material for research and development	Link	✓	-	✓	-	✓
- <u>ISO 24088-1:2022</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking of microorganisms — Part 1: Bacteria and archaea	Link	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- <u>ISO/WD 20309</u> Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for deep-sea biological materials	Link	na	na	na	na	na
Analysis (ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology)[#]						
- <u>ISO 20397-1:2022</u> Biotechnology - Massively parallel sequencing - Part 1: Nucleic acid and library preparation	Link	✓	✓	-	-	-
- <u>ISO 20397-2:2021</u> Biotechnology - Massively parallel sequencing - Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO/CD 20397-3</u> Biotechnology - Massively parallel sequencing - Part 3: General requirements and guidance for metagenomics	Link	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Data (ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology)						
- <u>ISO 21710:2020</u> Biotechnology - Specification on data management and publication in microbial resource centers	Link	✓	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO/TS 23494-1:2023</u> Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements	Link	-	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO/PWI TS 23494-2</u> Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 2: Common provenance model	Link	-	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO 20691:2022</u> Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences	Link	-	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO/DTS 24420</u> General Requirements for Data Processing of Shotgun Metagenomics	Link	-	-	✓	-	-
- <u>ISO/TR 3985:2021</u> Biotechnology — Data publication — Preliminary considerations and concepts	Link	-	-	✓	-	-

Legend: ✓ = addressed (in detail or to a minor extent); - = not addressed; na = information not available; Abbreviations: ISO = International Organization for Standardization, CEN = European Committee for Standardization, QM = quality management, TC = Technical Committee, TS = Technical Specification, TR = Technical Report; PWI, AWI, WD = different developmental stages of standards; standards underlined = of major relevance for MICROBE Task T4.2 and should be acquired to read entire content; study document in more detail for WP4 T4.2; standards not underlined = major relevance for MICROBE in general or for other WPs (e.g. WP3 (data), WP5 (legal, ethical issues)); # = Part 1 of this standard series includes “microbiome” in the scope and was thus retrieved from keyword-based search;

The standards listed in Table 3 are

- **relevant** for the “development of a guidance document for sample pre-analytics” (i.e. Task T4.2 of MICROBE); some standards are considered highly relevant (underlined in Table 3) and will be purchased to allow investigation of the entire content before writing the guidance documents; or
- **interesting** for other MICROE WPs such as WP3 “Data infrastructure for the microbiome biobanking” or WP5 “Legal and ethical framework - biobanking of microbiome samples”.

Human microbiomes

The only two standards that directly address the pre-analytical phase of samples intended for microbiome analysis are from the human microbiome field:

- **CEN/TS 17626:2022** *Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations - Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimen - Isolated microbiome DNA* (published in 2022)
- **ISO/TS 18701** *Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA* (currently under development at an early stage (AWI standing for ‘Approved Work Item’).

CEN/TS 17626:2022 was developed in the context of the EU project SPIDIA4P⁸ (Grant no. 733112). According to the Vienna Agreement, this European standard is currently being developed to an ISO standard (i.e. ISO/TS 18701), which will replace CEN/TS 17626. MUG had/has a leading role in the development of both standards.

These standards will serve as templates for WP4.

Soil, marine water and plants/seeds microbiomes

There are no standards that explicitly address the entire pre-analytical phase of soil, marine water or plant/seed samples for microbiome analysis.

Standards for other sample types often

- are not specific for samples intended for microbiome analysis but for other examinations;
- or do not cover the entire pre-analytical phase with all its factors within one standard document.

Still, several of these standards seem to be **worth looking at in more detail while developing guidance documents for the microbiome research field (T4.2)** (see Table 3). They address general pre-analytical aspects, and the table of content reveals which might be of importance for the microbiome research field, too. These are, for example, the documentation of pre-analytical information about the collection site, the sampling process, and the storage, transport or handing of samples.

For soil, numerous standards exist and there is a dedicated Technical Committee for soil, i.e. ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, with several Subcommittees (e.g. SC 7 Impact assessment with Working

⁸ SPIDIA/SPIDIA4P, www.spidia.eu

Group Sampling, SC 4 Biological characterization, SC 3 Chemical and physical characterization). Most standards address soil quality properties and/or analysis other than microbiome-related ones. Examples are standards for the analysis of chemical or physical properties or for the influence of soil substances on certain microorganisms.

Also for water quality, there is a dedicated ISO Technical Committee, i.e. ISO/TC 147 Water quality, with several Subcommittees (e.g. SC 4 Microbiological methods and SC 6 Sampling (general methods). Most standards are not for marine water or address other marine sample types (e.g. marine sediment, algae or macrofauna). ISO 5667-9:1992 Water quality — Sampling — Part 9: Guidance on sampling from marine waters explicitly excludes microbiome samples.

There are standards for seeds, however, they do not refer to the seed microbiome but are about seed oil quality or seed specification related to spices or herbs. With respect to plants, there is a new standard for plant biobanking which clearly covers the pre-analytical phase of various plant parts (incl. seeds), however it does not explicitly address the microbiome. Still, it is considered very helpful as a general template for T4.2. with respect to general pre-analytical steps and factors.

Biobanking, analysis, data

Standards for analytical methods and for biobanking quality management also contain chapters on sample pre-analytical steps and should therefore be consulted in detail in T4.2.

The biobanking quality management standards listed in Table 3 are, in general, pertinent for microbiome biobanks/resource centers and, thus, for other MICROBE WPs (e.g. WP5 “*Legal and ethical framework*”).

Standards on data may contain requirements concerning the pre-analytical data to be documented and should be included in the T4.2 guidelines. Moreover, these are relevant for WP3 “*Data infrastructure for the microbiome biobanking*”.

Other

The keyword search also retrieved standards for different life sciences fields and sample types such as food, water, cosmetics, air, textile, plastics, paper, petroleum, etc.

For food samples, a plethora of standards exist, however the vast majority is not for microbiome but for food quality control. Standards exist, for example, for the microbiology of food chain or animal feedstuffs, for surface sampling and microorganism analysis, or for specific food samples like milk, yoghurt, and butter.

Further information on the standards is provided in the Annex. This includes chapters with the matrices describing (highly) relevant standards (“hits highly relevant”) in more detail and the inventories ISO and CEN standards “hits related to the topic” which were evaluated as less relevant for MICROBE.

3.2 Guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics

About guidelines and best practices

Guidelines and best practices differ from ISO and CEN standards. Standards sum up the requirements to quality management aspects (e.g. pre-analytical quality or a quality management system). Best practices and guidelines describe how these quality management aspects can be integrated into laboratory processes. In general, best practices describe the ‘a best particular way of doing something’ (Osburn et al., 2011) and refer to ‘working methods that are officially accepted as being the best’ (Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 2023) in a particular field. They are typically generated by specialist groups in organizations, (EU) research projects, or other initiatives (e.g. ISBER; OECD, MIRRI, MicroB3, Australian Microbiome, etc.). Like standards, guidelines and best practices are not legally binding. Most guidelines and best practices are voluntary, but some can be mandatory or at least binding for a certain community, like (certain) OECD guidelines for their member states. (OECD, 2023).

Inventory of guidelines and best practices

MUG retrieved the guidelines and best practices from websites of organizations (e.g. research infrastructures or companies), EU projects, or initiatives (see Table 4 under ‘source’) and from scientific literature (e.g. books or journals). In addition, handbooks, being compendiums of procedures and protocols, were included in the inventory if they addressed the pre-analytical phase of samples intended for microbiome analysis.

Table 4 shows the inventory and gives an overview of the guidelines and best practices identified as relevant. It comprises documents for “biobanks/biological resource centers”, “soil”, “microbiome/microorganism”, “pre-analytical handling” and “reporting or coding” of (pre-analytical) data.

A detailed description (matrix) of (highly) relevant guidelines/best practices is provided in the Annex file.

Table 4: Main guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics

Guideline Topic (Source, Year of Publication)	Link	Sample Types Addressed	Content Addressed				
			Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data Issues	Ethics /Legal Issues	Other Bio-bank Issues
Biobanks/Biological Resource Center							
- Biodiversity Biobanking - A Handbook on Protocols and Practices (Synthesys, 2023)	Link	soil, water, plants, others	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
- ISBER Biobanking Best Practises Recommendations for Repositories (ISBER, 2017)	Link	human (plant, micro-organisms)	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- NCI Best Practices for Biospecimen Resources (NCI, 2016)	Link	human, micro-organisms	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- IARC Common minimum technical standards and protocols for biobanks dedicated to cancer research (IARC, 2012)	Link	human	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- OECD Best Practice Guidelines for biological resource centres (OECD, 2007)	Link	human, microorganisms	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
Microbiome/Microorganisms							
- Best practices in the use and exchange of microorganism biological control genetic resources (Mason P.G., 2023)	Link	microorganisms	-	-	-	✓	-
- Ausmicrobiome Scientific Manual (Australian Microbiome Initiative, 2022)	Link	soil, water	✓	✓	✓	-	-
- Book 'The Plant Microbiome: Methods and Protocols' (Carvalhais & Dennis, 2021)	Link	plant	✓	✓	-	-	-
- How to Plan and Conduct a Microbiome Study (Microbiome Insights Ltd., 2020)	Link	human, soil, water	✓	✓	✓	-	-
- Earth Microbiome Project - Protocols & Standards (EMP, 2017)	Link	human, soil, water, plant, other	✓	-	✓	-	-
- Best Practices - Access and Benefit Sharing of Microorganisms (MIRRI, 2016)	Link	microorganisms	✓	-	✓	✓	-

Guideline Topic (Source, Year of Publication)	Link	Sample Types Addressed	Content Addressed				
			Pre- analytics & QM	Ana- lysis	Data Issues	Ethics /Legal Issues	Other Bio- bank Issues
Microbiome/Microorganisms (continued)							
- World Federation for Culture Collections WFCC Guidance (WFCC; 2010)	Link	microorganisms	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
- <u>Marine Microbial Biodiversity, Bioinformatics & Biotechnology 'Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) Handbook'</u> (EU project 'Micro B3', №.287589)	Link	marine	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
- International Microbiome and Multi-Omics Standards Alliance & National Institute of Standards and Technology – webinars, workshops (IMMSA, cofounder & leader NIST)	Link	na	na	na	na	na	na
- International Human Microbiome Standards (IHMS) Standard Operation Procedures (IMSCSA EU project grant no. 964590)	Link	human	✓	✓	✓	-	-
- Human Microbiome Project SOPs (NIH HMP, 2010)	Link	human	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Soil Characterization							
- <u>Handbook: Protocols for sampling – general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis</u> (EU project 'SoildiverAgro', №.817819)	Link	soil	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
- <u>Handbook on case studies set up, protocols for sampling, sample procedure and analysis</u> (EU project 'SoildiverAgro', №.817819)	Link	soil	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Reporting, Coding							
- Reporting guidelines for human microbiome research: the STORMS checklist (STORMS Consortium, 2021)	Link	human	✓	✓	✓	-	-
- SPREC - Standard PREanalytical Code (<i>sample treatment codes</i>) (ISBER, 2012)	Link	human	✓	-	-	-	-
- BRISQ Guidelines (<i>reporting of data elements</i>) (Moore HM et al., 2011)	Link	human	✓	-	✓	-	-

Legend: ✓ = addressed (in detail or to a minor extent); - = not addressed; na = information not available; QM = quality management; guidelines/best practices underlined = of major relevance for MICROBE Task T4.2 and should be acquired to read entire content; study document in more detail for WP4 T4.2; guidelines/best practices not underlined = of major relevance for MICROBE in general or for other WPs (e.g. WP3 (data), WP5 (legal, ethical issues));

4. Conclusion

The landscape of standards, guidelines and best practices for human, soil, food and water sample types, as well as for biobanking and data, is manifold.

This report gives an overview of ISO and CEN standards, guidelines and best practices of relevance for the Task T4.2 of MICROBE. These will be considered further, and their entire content will be studied for information on pre-analytical requirements and recommendations.

This report also gives an overview of ISO and CEN standards, guidelines and best practices of interest for other MICROBE WPs such as WP3 *“Data infrastructure for the microbiome biobanking”* or WP5 *“Legal and ethical framework - biobanking of microbiome samples”*.

While numerous documents were retrieved by the keyword-based search, only a small proportion addresses the pre-analytics of samples for microbiome analysis or biobanking.

For human microbiome samples, very specific standards already exist (CEN/TS 17626) or are under development (ISO/AWI TS 18701). MICROBE (represented through MUG) will further support this development.

In several Technical Committees, new standards are in preparation. This accounts particularly for biobanking (and data) standards, most of which are developed in ISO/TC 276. MICROBE will further monitor the standard landscape and try to actively engage with respective Technical Committees and contribute to the standard development.

For the non-human microbiome sample types, the standards gap should be filled. MICROBE will address this by developing guidance documents for the defined sample types, namely soil, marine water and/or seeds. The human standards should serve as a template. Some standards, guidelines and best practices identified as relevant will be considered as references.

5. Annexes

5.1 Matrices of relevant International and pan-European (ISO and CEN) quality standards microbiome sample pre-analytics

The relevant documents are described in detail below. **Text in blue** indicates pre-analytical content.

Human microbiome

ISO/AWI TS 18701 Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA					
Sample types addressed: Human			Topic: Sample pre-analytics		
ISO or CEN Technical Committee:		Human ISO/TC 212 Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems, WG4			
Content addressed	Pre-analytics &		Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	QM	Analysis			
Scope – Description	✓		✓		
Scope – Target Group	<p>This standard specifies requirements and gives recommendations for the pre-examination phase of human specimens, such as stool, saliva, skin and urogenital specimens, intended for microbiome DNA examination. The pre-examination phase includes but is not limited to specimen collection, handling, transport, storage, processing, isolation of DNA, and documentation.</p> <p>It is applicable to molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations performed by medical laboratories. It is also intended to be used by health institutions, including facilities collecting and handling specimens, laboratory customers, in vitro diagnostics developers and manufacturers, <u>biobanks, institutions and commercial organizations performing biomedical research</u>, and regulatory authorities;</p> <p>NOT for microbiome DNA examination from tissue (e.g. biopsies)</p>				
Table of Content	Not publicly available because the standard is under development				

CEN/TS 17626:2022-01 Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations – Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimen – Isolated microbiome DNA

Sample types addressed: Human

Topic: Sample pre-analytics

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: CEN/TC 140 – In vitro diagnostic systems, WG3

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope – Description	✓		✓		
Scope – Target Group	<p>This standard specifies requirements and gives recommendations for the pre-examination phase of human specimens, such as stool, saliva, skin and urogenital specimens, intended for microbiome DNA examination. The pre-examination phase includes but is not limited to specimen collection, handling, transport, storage, processing, isolation of DNA, and documentation.</p> <p>It is applicable to molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations performed by medical laboratories. It is also intended to be used by health institutions, including facilities collecting and handling specimens, laboratory customers, in vitro diagnostics developers and manufacturers, biobanks, institutions and commercial organizations performing biomedical research, and regulatory authorities;</p> <p>NOT for microbiome DNA examination from tissue (e.g. biopsies).</p>				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions / 4 General 5 Outside the laboratory 5.1 Specimen collection 5.1.1 General 5.1.2 Information about the patient/specimen donor 5.1.3 Specific information about the patient/specimen donor 5.1.4 Selection of specimen collection method and device(s) 5.1.5 Specimen collection from the patient/specimen donor and specimen stabilization 5.2 Specimen storage and transport 5.2.1 General 5.2.2 Using collection devices with stabilizers 5.2.3 Using collection devices without stabilizers 6 Inside the laboratory 6.1 Specimen reception 6.2 Processing of specimens 6.3 Specimen storage before microbiome DNA isolation 6.4 Isolation of microbiome DNA 6.4.1 General 6.4.2 Using a commercial kit 6.4.3 Using a laboratory developed procedure 6.5 Quantity and quality assessment of isolated microbiome DNA 6.5.1 General 6.5.2 Quantity assessment 6.5.3 Quality assessment 6.6 Storage of isolated microbiome DNA 6.6.1 General 6.6.2 Microbiome DNA isolated using a commercial kit 6.6.3 Microbiome DNA isolated using a laboratory developed procedure <u>Annex A</u> (informative) Impact of various pre-analytical variables on microbiome DNA quantity, quality and profile</p>				

Biobanking

ISO 20387:2018 Biotechnology — Biobanking — General requirements for biobanking

Sample types addressed: Various

Topic: Biobanking, QM (System)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓		✓	✓	✓

Scope – Description This standard specifies **general requirements for the competence, impartiality and consistent operation of biobanks**, including quality control requirements to ensure biological material and data collection of appropriate quality.

Scope – Target Group It is applicable **to all organizations performing biobanking**, including biobanking of biological material **from multicellular organisms (e.g. human, animal, fungus and plant) and microorganisms for research and development.**

Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p><u>4 General requirements</u></p> <p>4.1 General / 4.2 Impartiality / 4.3 Confidentiality</p> <p><u>5 Structural requirements</u></p> <p><u>6 Resource requirements</u></p> <p>6.1 General</p> <p>6.2 Personnel</p> <p>6.3 Facilities/dedicated areas and environmental conditions</p> <p>6.4 Externally provided processes, products and services</p> <p>6.5 Equipment</p> <p><u>7 Process requirements</u></p> <p>7.1 General</p> <p>7.2 Collection of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7.3 Reception and distribution of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7.4 Transport of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7.5 Traceability of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7.6 Preparation and preservation of biological material</p> <p>7.7 Storage of biological material</p> <p>7.8 Quality control of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7.9 Validation and verification of methods</p> <p>7.10 Management of information and data</p> <p>7.11 Nonconforming output</p> <p>7.12 Report requirements</p> <p>7.13 Complaints</p> <p><u>8 Quality management system requirements</u></p> <p>8.1 Options</p> <p>8.2 Documented information for the quality management system (Option A)</p> <p>8.3 Control of quality management system documents (Option A)</p> <p>8.4 Control of records (Option A)</p> <p>8.5 Actions to address risks and opportunities (Option A)</p> <p>8.6 Improvement (Option A)</p> <p>8.7 Corrective action for nonconforming output (Option A)</p> <p>8.8 Internal audits (Option A)</p> <p>8.9 Quality management reviews (Option A)</p> <p><u>Annex A Documentation requirements</u></p> <p>Annex B Implementation guidance for Annex A</p>
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ISO/TR 22758:2020 Biotechnology — Biobanking — Implementation guide for ISO 20387

Sample types addressed: Various Topic: Biobanking, QM (System)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓		✓	✓	✓

Scope – Description
 This standard provides **guidance to biobanks on how to implement** the quality management, management, and technical requirements of **ISO 20387**. It expands on aspects of ISO 20387 and **provides examples for illustration purposes**. The aim of this document is to assist biobanks in addressing the competency of personnel and the appropriate quality of biological material and data collection. This document is equally applicable to newly established and existing biobanks.

Scope – Target Group
 It is applicable to all organizations performing biobanking, including biobanking of biological material from multicellular organisms (e.g. human, animal, fungus and plant) and microorganisms for research and development. It is equally applicable to **newly established and existing biobanks**.

Table of Content

- Foreword / Introduction
- 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions
- 4 Background information for the development of ISO 20387
 - 4.1 General
 - 4.2 Intended audience for ISO 20387 and this document
 - 4.3 Implementation of ISO 20387
- 5 Fitness for the intended purpose (FIP) (ISO 20387:2018, 3.24) in biobanking
 - 5.1 General
 - 5.2 Fitness for the intended purpose and biological material and/or associated data (BMaD) life cycle
 - 5.3 Factors affecting fitness for the intended purpose
 - 5.4 Determination of the pre-arranged requirements for FIP
 - 5.5 Decision whether the biological material and associated data is truly fit for an intended purpose
- 6 Process landscape
- 7 Conformity with ISO 20387
 - 7.1 Scopes of Conformity
 - 7.2 Conformity Assessment (CA) Practices (General aspects and applicability for biobanks)
- 8 Guidance on the interpretation of selected ISO 20387:2018 text parts
 - 8.1 General Requirements (ISO 20387:2018, Clause 4)
 - 8.2 Structural requirements (20387:2018, Clause 5)
 - 8.3 Resource requirements (ISO 20387:2018, Clause 6)
 - 8.4 Process requirements (ISO 20387:2018, Clause 7)
 - 8.5 Quality management system requirements (ISO 20387:2018, Clause 8)
- Bibliography

ISO 21899:2020 Biotechnology — Biobanking — General requirements for the validation and verification of processing methods for biological material in biobanks

Sample types addressed: Various

Topic: Biobanking, QM (QC)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓				
Scope – Target Group	<p>It is intended for use in the implementation and validation of processing methods for biological materials;</p> <p>It does not apply to biological material intended for food/feed production, laboratories undertaking food/feed analysis, and/or therapeutic use.</p>				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions 4 <u>Abbreviated terms</u> 5 <u>General and resource requirements</u> 6 <u>Selection of processing methods</u> 7 <u>Processing method implementation</u> 7.1 Targets for method implementation 7.2 Processing method implementation 8 <u>Initial validation of a processing method</u> 8.1 General 8.2 Validation plan 8.3 Assays for properties of interest 8.4 Validation execution 8.5 Targets for processing method validation 8.6 Review and approval of validation report 9 <u>Further validation</u> 10 <u>Method verification</u> 11 <u>Ongoing monitoring of a processing method</u> 11.1 General 11.2 Frequency of the monitoring 11.3 Planning 11.4 Procedure of the systematic monitoring 11.5 Procedure of the periodic monitoring 11.6 External quality assessments (EQA)/Interlaboratory exercises 12 <u>Record keeping and archiving</u> Annex A Processing and testing methods Annex B Examples of validation plans Bibliography</p>				

ISO/TS 23105:2021 Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for the biobanking of plant biological material for research and development

Sample types addressed: Plants

Topic: Biobanking

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓		✓	✓	✓

Scope - Description
This standard specifies **requirements for the collection, preparation, preservation, transportation, storage, distribution and disposal of plant biological materials and associated data.**

It is **applicable only to biological material** that can be used for further processing of **biomolecules, e.g. nucleic acids, proteins and metabolites.**

Scope – Target Group
It is applicable to **all organizations performing plant biobanking for research and development.**

Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p>4 General requirements</p> <p>5 Biological material collection</p> <p>5.1 General</p> <p>5.2 Collection procedure</p> <p>5.3 Preparation of collection containers, tools, supplies, reagents and consumables</p> <p>5.4 Biological material traceability</p> <p>5.5 Collection</p> <p>6 Transport of biological material and associated data</p> <p>7 Preparation and preservation of biological material</p> <p>7.1 General</p> <p>7.2 Cutting, cleaning and bagging</p> <p>7.3 Desiccation</p> <p>7.4 Snap freezing and cryopreservation</p> <p>7.5 Fast or rapid drying</p> <p>7.6 Grinding</p> <p>7.7 Biological material preservation in protective solution</p> <p>8 Storage of biological material</p> <p>8.1 General</p> <p>8.2 Storage temperature</p> <p>8.3 Biological material multiplication</p> <p>8.4 Monitoring of biological material</p> <p>9 Distribution and disposal of biological material</p> <p>10 Information collection</p> <p>Annex A Typical biological material storage temperatures and storage durations</p> <p>Annex B Exemplary information table for plant biological material</p> <p>Bibliography</p>
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ISO 24088-1:2022 Biotechnology — Biobanking of microorganisms — Part 1: Bacteria and archaea

Sample types addressed: Microorganisms

Topic: Biobanking, QM (System)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓		✓	✓	✓

Scope - Description This standard specifies **requirements for the biobanking of bacteria and archaea**. It includes the [management of microbial material](#), associated data, as well as biosafety and biosecurity requirements.

Scope – Target Group Applicable to **all organizations performing biobanking with bacteria and archaea** used for research and development.

Does **not apply** to processing methods for microbial materials intended for **food/feed production**, laboratories undertaking **food/feed analysis or therapeutic use**.

Table of Content

- Foreword / Introduction
- 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions
- 4 General requirements
 - 4.1 General
 - 4.2 Legal requirements
 - 4.3 Health and safety
 - 4.4 Biosecurity and access
 - 4.5 Relocation of microbial materials
- 5 Personnel
- 6 Facilities
 - 6.1 General
 - 6.2 Biosafety cabinets
 - 6.3 Back-up storage facilities
- 7 Critical equipment for microbial biobanking
 - 7.1 General
 - 7.2 Calibration
 - 7.3 Incubators
 - 7.4 Refrigerators
 - 7.5 Ultra-low temperature electrically powered storage
 - 7.6 Liquid nitrogen storage system/liquid nitrogen supply
 - 7.7 Freeze dryer
 - 7.8 Automated storage systems
 - 7.9 Autoclave
- 8 Process requirements
 - 8.1 Acquisition or deposit
 - 8.2 Authentication
 - 8.3 Purity and passage control
 - 8.4 Preparation, preservation and storage
 - 8.5 Distribution
 - 8.6 Packaging
 - 8.7 Transport
- 9 Complaint management
- 10 Management of information and data
 - 10.1 Information system requirements
 - 10.2 Inventory management
- 11 Quality control, validation and verification
 - 11.1 General
 - 11.2 Quality control of processes, microbial materials and associated data

11.3 Validation and verification of methods
12 Reporting
Bibliography

ISO/WD 20309 Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for deep-sea biological materials

Sample types addressed: Marine Topic: Biobanking, QM (System)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	na	na	na	na	na
Scope - Description	This standard specifies requirements for the biobanking of deep-sea biological materials , including the collection, processing, transportation and storage of deep-sea biological materials .				
Scope – Target Group	It is applicable only to deep-sea biological materials that can be used for biomolecular processing, e.g. nucleic acids, proteins, and metabolites .				
	It is applicable to all organizations performing research and development on deep-sea biological material .				
Table of Content	Not publicly available because the standard is under development.				

Soil

ISO 11063:2020 Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (DNA extraction)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil Quality, SC 4 Biological characterization

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Content addressed	✓				
Scope - Description	<p>This standard specifies a method for direct extraction of DNA from soil samples to analyse the abundance and composition of microbial communities by various techniques of molecular biology, including real-time quantitative PCR (qPCR).</p> <p>This method is mainly dedicated to agricultural and forest soils. This method can possibly not be suitable for soils rich in organic matter (e.g. peat soils) or soils heavily polluted with organic pollutants or heavy metals.</p>				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p>4 Principle</p> <p>5 Test materials</p> <p>5.1 Soil</p> <p>5.2 Chemicals</p> <p>5.3 Buffers and reagents</p> <p>6 Apparatus</p> <p>7 Procedures</p> <p>7.1 Preparation of soil samples</p> <p>7.2 Mechanical and chemical lyses</p> <p>7.3 Protein precipitation</p> <p>7.4 Nucleic acid precipitation and washing</p> <p>7.5 Nucleic acid storage</p> <p>8 Estimation of soil DNA quality and quantity</p> <p>8.1 Soil DNA quality and purity</p> <p>8.2 Soil DNA quantity</p> <p>9 Validation of the extraction procedure</p> <p>10 Test report</p> <p>Annex A Differences between ISO 11063:2012 and the revised document for direct extraction of DNA from soil samples</p> <p>Annex B Possible methods to purify soil DNA extracts</p> <p>Bibliography</p>				

ISO 15903:2002 Soil quality — Format for recording soil and site information

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics
(reporting formats)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓		✓		
Scope – Target Group	The purpose of this International Standard is to achieve a high degree of harmonization in reporting results of on-site recording, sampling, on-site sample analyses and laboratory analyses of soil samples . To this end, it provides instructions for correctly specifying the quantities and units used to express the results of analyses, the methods used and their precision.				
Table of Content	This standard also provides information to allow unique referencing of the sample in both field and laboratory contexts in order to ensure the traceability of the results. na				
	Foreword / Introduction / 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions 4 Preamble <u>5 List of parameters</u> 5.1 General 5.2 Objectives of the investigation 5.3 General information 5.4 Site details 5.5 Quantitative on-site observations including additional and non-intrusive investigations 5.6 List of parameters recorded on-site and analyses undertaken on site 5.7 Details concerning the sample 5.8 Transport and storage of samples 5.9 List of laboratory analyses required and appropriate analytical procedures to be used 5.10 Laboratory reception and pretreatment 5.11 Quantitative laboratory information about the samples Bibliography				

ISO 18400-101:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 101: Framework for the preparation and application of a sampling plan

Sample types addressed: Topic: Pre-analytics (sampling plan)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 7 Impact assessment

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope – Description	✓		✓		
Scope – Target Group	<p>This standard specifies the procedural elements to be taken in the preparation and application of a sampling plan.</p> <p>The sampling plan describes, among other things, what laboratory samples are to be taken, how they are to be taken and from where they are to be taken in order that the objectives of the investigation programme can be achieved.</p> <p>It is applicable to the sampling of soil and soil material, more specifically, e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - soil in the landscape, - soil stockpiles, - potentially contaminated sites, - agricultural soils, - landfills, and - forest soils. 				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p>4 Preparation of a sampling plan</p> <p>4.1 Principle</p> <p>4.2 Key elements of a sampling plan</p> <p>5 Sampling</p> <p>5.1 Taking the samples</p> <p>5.2 Delivery</p> <p>6 Reporting</p> <p>6.1 Documenting the sampling plan</p> <p>6.2 Sampling record and report</p> <p>Annex A Checklist for the items to be addressed in a sampling plan</p> <p>Bibliography</p>				

ISO 18400-102:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 102: Selection and application of sampling techniques

Sample types addressed: Soil Topic: Pre-analytics (sampling technique & equipment)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions / 4 Principle</p> <p><u>5 General aspects</u></p> <p>5.1 Health and safety</p> <p>5.2 Preliminary information</p> <p><u>5.3 Sample types</u></p> <p><u>5.4 Sample size</u></p> <p><u>5.5 Available techniques</u></p> <p><u>6 Selection of sampling techniques</u></p> <p>6.1 General</p> <p>6.2 Drilling rigs and ancillary equipment</p> <p><u>7 General aspects of application</u></p> <p>7.1 General aspects of field work</p> <p>7.2 Environmental considerations</p> <p>7.3 Cross-contamination</p> <p>7.4 Preparing to sample</p> <p>7.5 Breaking out</p> <p>7.6 Collection of samples</p> <p>7.7 Transport, storage, and preservation of samples</p> <p>7.8 Backfilling of exploratory holes</p> <p>7.9 Disposal of waste materials</p> <p>7.10 Personnel</p> <p><u>8 Taking samples of top-soil and other near surface materials</u></p> <p>8.1 Undisturbed samples</p> <p>8.2 Disturbed samples</p> <p><u>9 Sampling at greater depth</u></p> <p>9.1 Undisturbed samples</p> <p>9.2 Disturbed samples</p> <p><u>10 Sampling stockpiles</u></p> <p>10.1 General</p> <p>10.2 Sampling equipment</p> <p><u>Annex A Application of particular techniques</u></p> <p><u>Annex B Manually and power-operated sampling equipment</u></p> <p><u>Annex C Illustration of some selected drilling and sampling equipment</u></p> <p><u>Annex D Sampling equipment for stockpiles</u></p> <p><u>Annex E Examples of large samplers</u></p>				

ISO 18400-105:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (sampling transport & storage)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions 4 Incorporation in the sampling plan 5 Preparing samples for consignment 5.1 General 5.2 Containers 5.3 Labels 5.4 Preservation of samples 5.5 Filling containers and preparing samples and containers for consignment and transport 5.6 Sealing and consignment 5.7 Preservation of samples 6 Preservation prior to transport 6.1 General requirements 6.2 Cooling and freezing 6.3 Airtight storage 6.4 Nitrogen atmosphere 6.5 Hazardous materials 7 Transport 7.1 General requirements 7.2 Special transportation requirements 8 Delivery Bibliography				

ISO/AWI 18400-105 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (sampling transport & storage)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓				
Scope – Target Group	Na				
Table of Content	not publicly available because the standard is under development				

ISO 18400-206:2018 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 206: Collection, handling and storage of soil under aerobic conditions for the assessment of microbiological processes, biomass and diversity in the laboratory

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (collection, handling, storage)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 4 Biological characterization

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Content addressed	✓				
Scope - Description	<p>This standard provides standard procedures for the collection, handling and storage of soil for subsequent biological testing under aerobic conditions in the laboratory. It applies to the collection, handling and storage for assessing the effects of soil on microorganisms, invertebrates (e.g. survival, reproduction, growth, behaviour) and plants (e.g. development, growth); This document describes how to minimize the effects of differences in temperature, water content, and availability of oxygen on aerobic processes as well as the fractionation of soil particles to facilitate reproducible laboratory determinations;</p> <p>NOT applicable to the handling of soil where anaerobic conditions need to be maintained throughout.</p>				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions 4 Procedure for the handling of soil samples to be used in laboratory tests with microorganisms, plants and invertebrates 4.1 Selection of sampling locations 4.2 Performance of a preliminary survey 4.3 Description of field site 4.4 Sampling conditions 4.5 Sampling methods 4.6 Sample marking 4.7 Transportation conditions 4.8 Soil processing in the laboratory 4.9 Storage conditions and storage periods 4.10 Pre-incubation 5 Sampling report Bibliography</p>				

ISO 18512:2007 Soil quality — Guidance on long and short term storage of soil samples

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (storage)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Content addressed	✓		✓		
Scope - Description	This standard gives guidance on how to store and preserve soil samples for laboratory determinations and how to prepare them for analysis after storage . Special emphasis is given to maximum storage times as a function of different storage conditions.				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions 4 General comments on soil storage 5 Change in soil properties during storage 6 Storage conditions 6.1 General 6.2 Light 6.3 Temperature 6.4 Humidity 6.5 Accessibility, security, documentation and quality control 6.6 Duration of storage 6.7 Containers and quantity of sample stored 6.8 Preparing the samples after storage 7 Stepwise scheme 8 Step A: Consideration of need for further analysis and duration of storage 9 Step B: Consideration of parameters				

ISO 18400-107:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 107: Recording and reporting

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (recording)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics &		Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	QM					
	✓			✓		

Scope - Description This standard specifies **the minimum information required for a sampling report independent of the purpose** of the investigation.

Scope – Target Group na

Table of Content

- Foreword / Introduction
- 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions / 4 General
- [5 Sampling plan](#)
- [6 Field activities](#)
 - 6.1 Technical requirements
 - 6.2 Site data
 - 6.3 Identification
 - 6.4 Sample description
 - 6.5 Sampling
 - 6.6 Transport and storage
- [7 Instructions to the laboratory](#)
- [8 Final reporting](#)
- Bibliography

ISO 18400-106:2017 Soil quality — Sampling — Part 106: Quality control and quality assurance

Sample types addressed: Soil

Topic: Pre-analytics (QA/QC)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 190 Soil quality, SC 2 Sampling

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓				

Scope - Description This standard provides **guidelines for quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) for soil sampling**. [...] under the ISO 18400-100 umbrella (level 1, level 2) and **gives guidance to methods** on level 3.

Scope – Target Group na

Table of Content	
	Foreword / Introduction
	1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions
	4 Quality assurance
	4.1 General
	4.2 Sampling process
	5 Procedures, documents and data
	5.1 Procedures
	5.2 Documents and data management
	5.3 Audits
	6 Personnel
	6.1 Knowledge and experience
	6.2 Safety /
	7 Communication
	8 Equipment
	8.1 Choice of equipment and general requirements for use
	8.2 Calibration of equipment and servicing
	8.3 Influence on results
	9 Taking samples
	9.1 Sampling
	9.2 Quality control samples
	9.3 Preservation
	9.4 Storage and transport
	Bibliography

Data

ISO 21710:2020 Biotechnology — Specification on data management and publication in microbial resource centers

Sample types addressed: na

Topic: Data (management, publication)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓		✓		

Scope - Description This standard specifies **requirements for data management and publication in microbial resource centres (MRCs)** to enable consistent formatting and a quality control workflow to improve the overall quality of data. It also provides recommendations for MRCs to improve data sharing and integration of microbial material and associated data.

This document is intended to facilitate **procedures such as accessioning, acquisition, authentication, preservation, storage, and distribution** and can be used by MRCs, regulatory authorities, organizations, and schemes using peer-assessment to confirm or recognize the competence of MRCs in data management and publication.

Scope – Target Group na

Table of Content	1 Scope 2 Normative references 3 Terms and definitions
	4 Data publication in MRCs
	4.1 General requirements and recommendations for data publication
	4.2 Data fields of catalogue
	5 Data management and data quality control
	5.1 General
	5.2 Requirements for in-house data management
	5.3 Data management for the patent deposit of microbial material and associated data
	5.4 Data management requirements for the transfer and traceability of microbial material and associated data
	5.5 Unique identifier of microbial material and associated data
	5.6 Data quality control
	Annex A Recommended data sets
	A.1 Name and taxonomy of microbial material
	A.2 Strain administration
	A.3 Environment and history
	A.4 Biological interactions
	A.5 Sexuality
	A.6 Properties
	A.7 Genotype and genetics
	A.8 Growth conditions
	A.9 Application
	A.10 Bibliographic table

ISO/TS 23494-1:2023 Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements

Sample types addressed:	na	Topic: Data (provenance)
ISO or CEN Technical Committee:	ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology	
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis
		Data issues
		✓
		Ethics/legal issues
		Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	<p>This standard specifies a general concept for a provenance information model for biological material and data and requirements for provenance data interoperability and serialization.</p> <p>The provenance information model covers any information relevant to the quality and fitness for purpose of the biological material generated throughout the pre-analytical phase of the materials life cycle from collection to analysis, data originating from analytical procedures applied to the biological material and results from further mathematical processing of the data.</p>	
Scope – Target Group	<p>This document is applicable to organizations, authorities and industries that are:</p> <p>a) collecting, processing or distributing biological material for research; b) generating, collecting, analysing or storing data on biological material.</p>	
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p><u>4 Requirements and recommendations on provenance information management</u></p> <p>4.1 Provenance information generation</p> <p>4.2 Provenance information availability and findability</p> <p>4.3 Provenance information accessibility</p> <p>4.4 Requirements for the computer infrastructure</p> <p>Bibliography</p>	

ISO/PWI TS 23494-2 Biotechnology — Provenance information model for biological material and data — Part 2: Common provenance model

Sample types addressed:	na	Topic: Data (provenance)
ISO or CEN Technical Committee:	ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology	
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis
		Data issues
		✓
		Ethics/legal issues
		Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	na – possible new standard to come	
Scope – Target Group	na – possible new standard to come	
Table of Content	na – possible new standard to come	

ISO 20691:2022 Biotechnology — Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences

Sample types addressed: Human, non-human

Topic: Data (formatting)

ISO or CEN Technical Committee: ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
			✓		

Scope - Description
This standard specifies **requirements for the consistent formatting and documentation of data and corresponding metadata** (i.e. data describing the data and its context) **in the life sciences**, including biotechnology, and biomedical, as well as **non-human biological research** and development. It provides guidance on rendering data in the life sciences findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (F-A-I-R).

Scope – Target Group
It is **applicable to many domains in biotechnology and the life sciences** including, but not limited to: **basic/applied research** in all domains of the life sciences, and **industrial, medical, agricultural, or environmental biotechnology** (excluding for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes), as well as methodology-driven domains, such as **genomics** (including massive parallel sequencing, metagenomics, epigenomics and functional genomics), **transcriptomics, translomics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics, glycomics, enzymology, immunochemistry, synthetic biology, systems biology, systems medicine and related fields.**

Table of Content

- Foreword / Introduction
- 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions
- 4 Recommendations and requirements for the description of entities and concepts in life science data
 - 4.1 General
 - 4.2 Recommended ubiquitous identifier scheme for biological and conceptual entities
 - 4.3 Formatting data and contextual descriptive data (metadata) for biological entities and concepts
- 5 Technical and organizational recommendations and requirements for data formats
 - 5.1 General
 - 5.2 Organizational responsibilities
 - 5.3 Documentation
 - 5.4 Versioning and change log
 - 5.5 Compatibility
 - 5.6 Extensibility
 - 5.7 Compression
 - 5.8 Structural and control elements
 - 5.9 Requirements for data types within formats
 - 5.10 Consistency and compatibility
 - 5.11 Data integrity
 - 5.12 Format validation
 - 5.13 Data provenance
- 6 Semantic recommendations and requirements for data formats
 - 6.1 General
 - 6.2 Minimum consensus information for annotation of biological data
 - 6.3 Syntax and reification
- 7 Requirements for terminologies and ontologies suitable for annotation of biological data
 - 7.1 General
 - 7.2 Requirements for biological ontologies
- 8 Requirements for domain specific data standards
 - 8.1 General
 - 8.2 Specific requirements for domain specific data standards

9 Requirements for data repositories for biological data

9.1 General

9.2 Requirements for data repositories of biological data

Annex A Examples of common formats for life science data

A.1 General

A.2 Data formats for OMICS, biochemical and molecular biology methods

A.3 Formats for biological imaging

A.4 Formats for computer models of biological systems

A.5 Formats for model simulations and their results in the life sciences

A.6 Descriptors for quality measurements for data and models

Annex B Minimum reporting standards for data, models and metadata

ISO/DTS 24420 General Requirements for Data Processing of Shotgun Metagenomics

Sample types addressed: Human, non-human		Topic		Data (formatting)
ISO or CEN Technical Committee	ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology			
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues ✓	Ethics/legal issues
Scope - Description	<p>This standard illustrates the workflow of shotgun metagenomic sequence data processing of host-derived microbiome and environmental metagenomes;</p> <p>It specifies the requirements for quality control of shotgun metagenomic sequence data processing for massively parallel DNA sequencing.</p>			
Scope – Target Group	na			
Table of Content	<p>Foreword / Introduction</p> <p>1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions</p> <p><u>4 Processing workflow</u></p> <p><u>5 Data processing</u></p> <p>5.1 Facilities and software requirements</p> <p>5.2 Sequence quality control and error determination</p> <p>5.3 Sequence assembly</p> <p><u>6 Data analysis</u></p> <p>6.1 Annotation</p> <p>6.2 Calculation of species relative abundance</p> <p><u>7 Data archive and metadata</u></p> <p>7.1 Original data</p> <p>7.2 Sequencing analytical data</p> <p>7.3 Data directory and archive</p> <p>7.4 Metadata</p> <p><u>Annex</u></p>			

ISO/TR 3985:2021 Biotechnology — Data publication — Preliminary considerations and concepts

Sample types addressed: Human, non-human	Topic	Data (formatting)
ISO or CEN Technical Committee	ISO/TC 276 Biotechnology	

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
			✓		

Scope - Description

This standard **reviews best practices** that:

- a) respect the **existing standardization efforts** of life sciences research communities;
- b) normalize **key aspects of data description** particularly at the level of the biology being studied (and shared) across the life sciences communities;
- c) ensure that **data are “findable” and useable** by other researchers; and
- d) provide guidance and metrics for **assessing** the applicability of a particular **data sharing plan**.

Scope – Target Group

It is applicable to domains in **life sciences including biotechnology, genomics** (including massively parallel nucleotide sequencing, metagenomics, epigenomics and functional genomics), **transcriptomics, translaticomics, proteomics, metabolomics, lipidomics, glycomics, enzymology, immunochemistry**, life science imaging, **synthetic biology, systems biology, systems medicine and related fields**.

Table of Content

Foreword / Introduction

1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions

4 Abbreviated terms

5 Principles

5.1 General

5.2 Current technologies, approaches and their flaws

5.3 Standards and best practices to facilitate data sharing and reuse

5.4 Additional desirable attributes

5.5 Essential considerations

5.5 Essential considerations

6 Major challenges

6.1 General

6.2 Domain

6.3 Regionalization

6.4 Proprietary data

6.5 Large number of existing bio-ontologies, controlled vocabularies and terminologies

6.6 Large number of existing data repositories and corresponding domain specific data formats

6.7 Large number of funding agencies (e.g. national, educational, philanthropic, commercial)

7 Examples of existing national and regional standards or requirements for data sharing or publication

7.1 General / 7.2 USA / 7.3 Canada / 7.4 European Union / 7.5 Germany / 7.6 China / 7.7 United Kingdom / 7.8 India / 7.9 Japan

8 Existing legal requirements for data protection

8.1 USA

8.2 European Union

9 Timing of data publication

10 Costs of data publication

11 Archival data

12 Validation and verification of compliance

13 Affected stakeholder categories

Annex A Searchability of scientific content on the web

A.1 Word and phrase search

A.2 Search using ontological terms

Annex B Example enhanced annotation of text documents

Bibliography

Plants

CEN/TS 17708:2022 Plant biostimulants - Preparation of sample for microbial analysis

Sample types addressed:	Plant	Topic	Plant (micro-organism preparation)
ISO or CEN Technical Committee	CEN/TC 455/WG 3		
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues
	✓	✓	□
Scope - Description	This document defines general rules for the aerobic preparation of the initial suspension and of dilutions for microbiological examinations of microbial plant biostimulants.		
Scope – Target Group	na		
Table of Content	European foreword / Introduction 1 Scope / 2 Normative references / 3 Terms and definitions <u>4 Principle</u> <u>5 Diluents</u> <u>6 Apparatus</u> 7 Sampling and storage <u>8 Preparation of samples and suspension</u> 8.1 Protocol for enumeration of beneficial microorganisms 8.2 Protocol for enumeration of not-desirable microorganisms 8.3 Protocol for the determination of anaerobic plate count 8.4 Protocol for the detection of pathogenic microorganisms 8.5 Further dilutions 8.6 Duration of the procedure <u>Annex A (informative) Plating procedure</u> <u>Annex B (informative) Diluents for general use</u> Bibliography		

Analytical methods

ISO 20397-1:2022 Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing — Part 1: Nucleic acid and library preparation

Sample types addressed: na Topic Analysis

ISO or CEN Technical Committee (TC) ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics &		Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	QM	Analysis			
Scope - Description	✓	✓	-	-	-
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	Foreword / Introduction 1 Scope 2 Normative references 3 Terms and definitions 4 Nucleic acid sample quality evaluation 4.1 General 4.2 Sample quantification 4.3 Sample purity 4.4 Sample integrity 5 Nucleic acid library preparation 5.1 General 5.2 Fragmentation 5.3 Addition of universal sequences 5.4 Size selection 5.5 Amplification 5.6 Purification and clean up procedures 5.7 Library quantification 5.8 Library qualification 6 Validation 7 Reference materials or controls 7.1 General 7.2 Control samples 7.3 Positive control 7.4 Negative control 7.5 No-template control 7.6 Spike-in control 7.7 Reference materials 8 Contaminations 8.1 General 8.2 Primary sample evaluation 8.3 Protocol and operation procedure Annex A Checklist for sample quality assessment before library construction Annex B Examples of quality criteria for selected MPS platforms and applications Annex C Reference material list Bibliography				

ISO 20397-2:2021 Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing — Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data

Sample types addressed: na Topic Analysis

ISO or CEN Technical Committee (TC) ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology

Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Content addressed	✓	-	✓	-	-
Scope - Description	This standard specifies general requirements and recommendations for quality assessments and control of massively parallel sequencing (MPS) data . It covers post raw data generation procedures, sequencing alignments, and variant calling; gives general guidelines for the validation and documentation of MPS data .				
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	Foreword / Introduction <u>1 Scope</u> <u>2 Normative references</u> <u>3 Terms and definitions</u> <u>4 Raw data</u> 4.1 General 4.2 Raw data file 4.3 Quality assessment of raw data 4.4 Raw data pre-processing <u>5 Sequence alignment and mapping</u> 5.1 General 5.2 Alignment and mapping file format 5.3 Quality control of sequencing alignment and mapping 5.4 Alignment post-processing <u>6 Variant calling</u> 6.1 General 6.2 Data file for variant calling 6.3 Quality metrics in the variant calling 6.4 Processing of false positive variants 6.5 Sequence annotation <u>7 Validation</u> 7.1 General 7.2 Validation of quality metrics <u>8 Documentation</u> Annex A Quality metrics for specific example MPS platforms Annex B Coverage and read recommendations by applications Annex C Software for sequence alignment and mapping Bibliography				

ISO/CD 20397-3 Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing — Part 3: General requirements and guidance for metagenomics

Sample types addressed:	na	Topic	Analysis		
ISO or CEN Technical Committee (TC)	ISO/TC 276 Bio-technology				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
Scope - Description	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Scope – Target Group	na				
Table of Content	not publicly available because the standard is under development				

5.2 Matrices of relevant guidelines/best practices for microbiome sample pre-analytics

The most relevant documents are described in detail below. **Text in blue** indicates pre-analytical content.

Biobanks/biological resource centers

Biodiversity Biobanking - A Handbook on Protocols and Practices					
Source, year of publication	Synthesys, 2023				
Sample types addressed	Soil, water, plants, others				
Link	https://www.synthesys.info/news-events/BiobankingPublications.html				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>This handbook was produced by the SYNTHESYS+ Network consortium. SYNTHESYS+ is a pan-European collections infrastructure project funded by the European Commission (Feb 2019 - Jan 2023). SYNTHESYS+ laid the foundations for the Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DISSCO), a massive scientific infrastructure project, with 115 European Museums from 21 countries positioning their collections. The project aimed to produce an accessible, integrated European resource for research users in the natural sciences.</p>				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'Biodiversity Biobanking - A Handbook on Protocols and Practices' aims to provide guidance and recommendations on field sampling, preservation, and storage of biomaterials along with management procedures.</p>				
Chapters	<p>Preface / Acknowledgments / Contributors to the Handbook List of abbreviations Chapter 1: Biobank Management Chapter 2: Metadata and Data Management. Chapter 3: Field Collection Chapter 4: Culture Preservation and Storage Methods Chapter 5: Cryopreservation Chapter 6: Freeze-drying or Lyophilisation Chapter 7: Retrieval from Preservation and Viability Assessments Chapter 8: DNA Chapter 9: High-Molecular-Weight DNA Chapter 10: DNA Assessment Chapter 11: Genomic Characterisation Chapter 12: Ethics References Annex I (Biobanks and Networks) Annex II (Further Information)</p>				
Relevance	<p>The handbook covers the main process steps of the pre-analytical phase in several chapters (marked in blue). It describes pre-analytical variables and gives recommendations for proper processing and/or documentation of data, which are based on scientific literature. Several sample types are addressed in the handbook, including soil, seed biobanking, aqueous samples and microbiome.</p> <p>The content will be helpful for WP4 T4.2.</p>				

ISBER Biobanking Best Practises Recommendations for Repositories

Source, year of publication	ISBER, 2017 (4th edition)*				
Sample types addressed	Human (plant, microorganisms)				
Link	https://www.isber.org/page/BPR				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM ✓	Analysis	Data issues ✓	Ethics/legal issues ✓	Other bio-bank issues ✓
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>The Biobanking Best Practices Recommendations were produced by ISBER, an organization and global biobanking forum that addresses scientific, technical, legal, and ethical issues for biobanks and biorepositories. ISBER's key activities include creating educational and training opportunities; providing a forum for the dissemination of state-of-the-art policies, processes, and research findings; and showcasing innovative technologies, products, and services. The fourth edition of the ISBER Best Practices was prepared by professionals at various organizations from around the world representing a diverse group of human, biodiversity, environmental, and veterinary repositories.</p>				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'ISBER Best Practices: Recommendations for Repositories Best Practices' is a guidance document, which presents effective practices for the management of specimen collections and repositories.</p>				
Chapters	<p>INTRODUCTION SECTION A: REPOSITORY PLANNING CONSIDERATIONS SECTION B: FACILITIES SECTION C: STORAGE AND PROCESSING EQUIPMENT SECTION D: QUALITY MANAGEMENT SECTION E: METHOD VALIDATION AND QUALITY CONTROL CONSIDERATIONS SECTION F: SAFETY SECTION G: TRAINING SECTION H: COST MANAGEMENT SECTION I: REPOSITORY INFORMATION MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS SECTION J: PACKAGING AND SHIPPING SECTION K: SPECIMEN COLLECTION, PROCESSING, RECEIVING, AND RETRIEVAL SECTION L: LEGAL AND ETHICAL ISSUES FOR BIOSPECIMENS SECTION M: SPECIMEN ACCESS, UTILIZATION, AND DISPOSITION REFERENCES APPENDIX A: INTERNET RESOURCES APPENDIX B: GLOSSARY APPENDIX C: ABBREVIATIONS</p>				
Relevance	<p>The Best Practices describe what biobanks and repositories need to consider with respect to biobank planning and operation.</p> <p>The document addresses the major pre-analytical phases, however, most content refers to human biobanking and there to tissues and body fluids. Microorganisms and plants are only to a minor extent addressed; microbiome-containing samples are not addressed.</p> <p>Still, the document may be interesting for MICROBE with respect to the general biobanking/repository content and for WP4 with respect to the chapters on quality management and quality control.</p> <p>It is good that the document is periodically reviewed and revised and content from other relevant documents such latest literature and ISO standards included.</p>				

Soil characterization

Handbook: Protocols for sampling – general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis					
Source, year of publication	SoildiverAgro' (H2020 project Grant N°. 817819), 2020				
Sample types addressed	Soil, (wheat)				
Link	http://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Handbook-WP3-PROTOCOLS-FOR-SAMPLING-GENERAL-SOIL-CHARACTERIZATION-AND-SOIL-BIODIVERSITY-ANALYSIS.pdf				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	✓	
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>The Handbook: Protocols for sampling – general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis was produced by SoildiverAgros, an EU H2020 project (grant no. 817819), as a deliverable of WP3 'Soil biodiversity assessment in European cropping systems'. Numerous people from various countries have participated in the realization of this handbook.</p>				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'Handbook: Protocols for sampling – general soil characterization and soil biodiversity analysis' produced by SoildiverAgros represents a compendium of methods, in which procedures for the determination of a series of soil and wheat properties are described. Each chapter of the handbook includes a first section with a slight explanation of the property to be determined, followed by a list with the necessary materials, a step-by-step explanation of the procedure in question, the calculations necessary to obtain the desired property, and a series of important tips or points to improve the procedure. Each chapter also includes a specific bibliography section.</p>				
Chapters	<p>1 Soil sampling 6 1.1. Sampling for bulk density 12 1.2. Sampling for general soil characteristics, microbial diversity and nematodes diversity 14 1.3. Sampling for earthworm diversity 2. Physical analyses [...] 3. SOIL Chemical Analyses [...] 4. Biological Analyses 4.1. Earthworm diversity / 4.2. Nematodes diversity 4.3. Microorganisms diversity - incl. DNA isolation 4.4. Whole microbial diversity: PLFA and NLFA 5. Wheat Quality Analyses 5.1. Wheat grain moisture / 5.2. Wheat specific weight 5.3. Weight of thousands grains (or seed index) / 5.4. Nitrogen and protein content of wheat grain</p>				
Relevance	<p>The Soil Handbook provides a practical overview of the whole procedure, including the soil sampling for microbiome diversity, the number of samples to be taken and several important pre-analytical details along pre-examination steps like transport, storage, DNA extraction and distribution of the necessary subsamples to the different partners for the analysis (chapters 1.2 and 4.3). It contains soil sample information sheets (Annex 1.1.). It is primarily for agricultural soil samples, which needs to be compared with requirements for other soil sample types. Overall, it is considered highly relevant for WP4 T4.2).</p>				

Handbook on case studies set up, protocols for sampling, sample procedure and analysis

Source, year of publication	SoildiverAgro' ((H2020 project Grant N°. 817819), 2020				
Sample types addressed	Soil, (crop)				
Link	http://soildiveragro.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Handbook-WP5-Handbook-on-case-studies-set-up-protocols-for-sampling-sample-procedure-and-analysis.pdf				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>The handbook on 'case studies set up, protocols for sampling, sample procedure and analysis was produced by SoildiverAgros, an EU H2020 project (grant no. 817819) as a deliverable to be used in WP5. Numerous people from various countries have participated in the realization of this handbook.</p>				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'Handbook on case studies set up, protocols for sampling, sample procedure and analysis' produced by SoildiverAgros represents a compendium of a defined series of standardized methodologies that allowed the project to obtain comparable results in one of their work packages.</p> <p>Each chapter of the handbook includes a first section with a slight explanation of the property to be determined, followed by a list with the necessary materials, a step-by-step explanation of the procedure in question, the calculations necessary to obtain the desired property, and a series of important tips or points to improve the procedure. Each chapter also includes a specific bibliography section.</p>				
Chapters	<p>1 Case studies setup and experimental management</p> <p>1.1. Experimental design</p> <p>1.2. Collection of technical data from experimental plots for the economic assessment</p> <p>2. Soil sampling general introduction</p> <p>2.1. Sampling for bulk density</p> <p>2.2. Sampling for general soil characteristics, microbial diversity and nematodes diversity</p> <p>2.3. Sampling for earthworm diversity</p> <p>3. Crop growth, incidence of pests/diseases and crop yield evaluation / 3.1. [...] - 3.3 [...]</p> <p>4. Crop quality and nutrition evaluation</p> <p>[..]</p> <p>5. Assessment of soil biodiversity</p> <p>5.1. Earthworm diversity</p> <p>5.2. Nematodes diversity</p> <p>5.3. Microorganisms diversity - incl. DNA extraction</p> <p>5.4. Whole microbial diversity: PLFA and NLFA</p> <p>6. Soil fertility and pollution assessment</p> <p>[..]</p> <p>7. Soil structure, water availability + soil carbon sequestration</p> <p>[..]</p> <p>8. Soil greenhouse gas emission</p>				
Relevance	<p>The Soil Handbook provides a practical overview of the whole procedure including the soil sampling for microbiome diversity, starting with the planning of the experimental design, definition of the spatial distribution and size of the plots, the size of the plots, the frequency of samplings, the proper timing, the number of soil samples collected in each sampling, the procedure to collect the samples and the pre-treatment of samples and DNA extraction for microbiome diversity determination. Overall, it is considered highly relevant for WP4 T4.2).</p>				

Microbiome/microorganisms

Ausmicrobiome Scientific Manual											
Source, year of publication	Australian Microbiome Initiative, 2020										
Sample types addressed	Soil, water										
Link	https://www.australianmicrobiome.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/AusMicrobiome_ScientificManual_May19_v1draft.pdf										
Content addressed	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pre-analytics & QM</th> <th>Analysis</th> <th>Data issues</th> <th>Ethics/legal issues</th> <th>Other bio-bank issues</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues	✓	✓	✓	-	-
Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues							
✓	✓	✓	-	-							
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>The Ausmicrobiome Scientific Manual was produced by the Australian Microbiome Initiative, which is a continental-scale, collaborative project aspiring to characterise the diversity and ecosystem service provision of the microorganisms inhabiting natural Australian ecosystems. The Australian Microbiome initiatives mission is to develop a public database of microbial diversity across a range of Australian terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The database shall deliver searchable information on the occurrence and distribution of potential microbiological resources, collated.</p> <p>The manual was generated with contribution from consortium members and/or service providers.</p>										
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'Ausmicrobiome Scientific Manual' lists and describes protocols/Standard Operating Procedures for different sample types and analysis that are applied or used by different Australian projects/networks/organizations. Protocols are provided for sample collection, extraction, purification and quantification of DNA/RNA from environmental and host samples. Sample types addressed include e.g. soil samples or costal seawater samples for microbiome (DNA or RNA) analysis.</p>										
Chapters	<p>Introduction Contributors Citations TABLE 1. Metadata Field Codes Summary 1. Sample Collection Procedures 2. Contextual Metadata Analytical Procedures 3. OMICS Sample Extraction, Purification and Quantification Procedures 4. OMICS Sequencing Procedures 5. Bioinformatics 6. Data Analyses 7. References</p>										
Relevance	<p>The Ausmicrobiome Manual is a collection of protocols offering a step-by-step guidance. The individual protocols were provided by the initiative consortium members and have been published in scientific journals. In addition, protocols also come from companies providing kits and/or instruments used for microbiome sample handling and/or analysis. The content is therefore evidence based.</p> <p>The protocols exist for certain soil and marine sample types and analyses. Some of the protocols are helpful as a reference for MICROBE partners and for WP4 T4.2. They give insight into pre-analytical workflow and steps. Moreover, they contain information on data/metadata to be gathered and codes for metadata fields and conversion formats and units, which are also relevant for WP5.</p>										

Marine Microbial Biodiversity, Bioinformatics & Biotechnology - 'Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) Handbook'

Source, year of publication	Micro B3 (EU project, Grant №.287589), 2016				
Sample types addressed	Marine				
Link	https://www.microb3.eu/sites/default/files/osd/OSD_Handbook_2016.pdf				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>The Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) Handbook' was produced by Micro B3 (Marine Microbial Biodiversity, Bioinformatics, Biotechnology), an EU 7FP project (grant no. 287589; Jan. 2012 - Dec 2015). Micro B3 develops innovative bioinformatic approaches and a legal framework to make large-scale data on marine viral, bacterial, archaeal and protists genomes and metagenomes accessible for marine ecosystems biology and to define new targets for biotechnological applications.</p> <p>Micro B3 is based on a strong user- and data basis from ongoing European sampling campaigns to long-term ecological research sites.</p> <p>The Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) is a simultaneous sampling campaign of the world's oceans, which took place in 2014, 2015 and 2016.</p>				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The 'Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) Handbook* is a best practice guide describing procedures and policies on the marine sample collection, logistics and bioinformatics. It was intended primarily for marine research stations and cruises contributing to the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) events (see above). The OSD Handbook guidelines contain standardised protocols accompanied by a standardised set of environmental parameters for molecular and morphological analysis of marine microbial samples.</p>				
Chapters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) Workflow 2. OSD Site Registration 3. OSD Data Sharing Policy 4. OSD Legal Permissions for Sampling 5. OSD Sampling Instructions & Protocols 6. OSD Mandatory and Recommended Information 7. Handling OSD Samples (shipping, sequencing and bio-archiving) 8. Submitting OSD Sample Contextual Data 9. OSD Environmental and Morphology-based Biodiversity Data 10. OSD Nucleotide Sequence Data 11. OSD Data Access and Analysis <p>References</p> <p>Annex I OSD Log sheets</p> <p>Annex II MTA – Agreement between OSD Participant and MPIMM</p> <p>Annex III MTA – Agreement between OSD Participant and SI NMNH</p> <p>Annex IV Model Agreement on Access to Marine Microorganisms and Benefit Sharing</p> <p>Annex V OSD Data Sharing Policy</p>				
Relevance	<p>The OSD Handbook provides a very good description of a marine sample collection process including a pre-analytical workflow description and a detailed list of pre-analytical data (environmental parameter; log sheets) to be documented. It also describes important legal requirements and process steps Therefore this document is highly relevant for WP4 T4.2 when marine water samples will be addressed. It also can be used as an example and template for their sample types such as soil. Moreover, it is relevant for WP5.</p>				

Best Practices - Access and Benefit Sharing of Microorganisms

Source, year of publication	MIRRI, 2016										
Sample types addressed	Microorganisms										
Link	https://www.mirri.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/ABSbestpracticemanual.pdf										
Content addressed	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pre-analytics & QM</th> <th>Analysis</th> <th>Data issues</th> <th>Ethics/legal issues</th> <th>Other bio-bank issues</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>✓</td> <td>-</td> <td>✓</td> <td>✓</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues	✓	-	✓	✓	-
Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues							
✓	-	✓	✓	-							
About the source (editors or authors)	<p>Best Practices - Access and Benefit Sharing of Microorganisms was produced by the Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure (MIRRI), a pan-European distributed research infrastructure. Aim of MIRRI is to provide facilitated access to high quality microorganism for research, development and application. Furthermore, MIRRI aims to connect public microbial domain Biological Resource Centers (mBRCs) with researchers, policy makers and other stakeholders to deliver biological material and services. MIRRI developed the Best Practice Manual in response to Article 20 of the Nagoya Protocol. It was primarily designed for the management of collections of living microbial strains and their derivatives (e.g. DNA samples), but could be useful for all who receive microorganisms, use and supply them to colleagues or others outside their institutions for further use.</p>										
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The MIRRI 'Best Practices - Access and Benefit Sharing of Microorganisms' provide guidance for microbial domain biological resource centers (mBRCs) in implementing their access and benefit sharing institutional policies. This is with regard to genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, and working procedures for the acquisition of material, including accession, i.e. formal acceptance of new material in the public collections of the mBRCs, for transfer of material including supply to third parties and the delivery of other services.</p>										
Chapters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction 2. MIRRI Best Practice on Access and Benefit Sharing (ABS) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1. Managing acquisition of biological material for accession into the public collection or other purposes <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1.1. Accession forms and Material Accession Agreements (MAA) 2.1.2. Tracking information 2.1.3. Checking documentation provided by the depositor 2.1.4. Special cases 2.1.5. Setting terms for utilization by the mBRC and third parties 2.1.6. Material acquired temporarily 2.2. Managing transfer of material from the public collection to other mBRCs or third parties <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2.2.1. Transfer of material between mBRCs (exchanges) 2.2.2. Transfer to third parties 2.2.3. Material collected post-CBD and pre-Nagoya 2.2.4. Tracing user information 2.2.5. Transfer to third parties by recipients 2.3. Access, internal use of material, and benefit sharing by the mBRC 2.4. Managing documentation and data 2.5. Training and awareness-raising 2.6. Managing secured collection 3. Glossary 4. Abbreviations 5. Annexes 										
Relevance	<p>The MIRRI Best Practices do not address pre-analytical process steps and associated factors, but seems to contain some information on data needed for accession/access procedures that could in part come from the pre-analytical phase. In this respect, it is worth discussing this document in T4.2. Moreover, it is relevant for the MICROBE WPs.</p>										

Reporting/coding

Reporting guidelines for human microbiome research: the STORMS checklist

Source, year of publication	STORMS Consortium, 2021				
Sample types addressed	Human				
Link	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-021-01552-x				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	-	-
About the source (editors or authors)	The STORMS reporting guidelines were developed by a multidisciplinary group of microbiome epidemiology researchers forming the STORM consortium.				
About the guideline/best practice document	Reporting guidelines for human microbiome research are a checklist - also called 'Strengthening The Organization and Reporting of Microbiome Studies' (STORMS) checklist. It provides guidance for concise and complete reporting of microbiome studies that will facilitate manuscript preparation, peer review, and reader comprehension of publications and comparative analysis of published results.				
Chapters	The tool is composed of a 17-item checklist organized into six sections that correspond to the typical sections of a scientific publication, presented as an editable table for inclusion in supplementary materials. These items include also pre-analytical factors that need to be documented (e.g. study design, participants, geographic location, relevant dates, inclusion exclusion criteria, antibiotic usage, sample size, specimen collection, transport/shipping, storage, laboratory methods, DNA extraction etc.				

BRISQ Guidelines (reporting of data elements)

Source, year of publication	(Moore HM et al., 2011)				
Sample types addressed	Human				
Link	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21433001/				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	✓	✓	-	-
About the source (editors or authors)	The BRISQ Guidelines were generated in a half-day workshop called "Development of Biospecimen Reporting Criteria for Publications", held at the National Cancer Institute (NCI) 2009 Biospecimen Research Network Symposium.				
About the guideline/best practice document	<p>The BRISQ Guidelines are best practices guidelines containing recommendations for the reporting of data elements for human biospecimens (solid tissues and bodily fluids). The data elements include information for documentation of classes of biospecimens and [pre-analytical] factors that could influence the integrity, quality, and/or molecular composition of biospecimens.</p> <p>The recommended data elements are intended to be reported by an author in a journal publication, by a company in a regulatory submission, or by a biorepository distributing biospecimens. They are intended to be applied in biomedical studies where human biospecimens are used.</p>				
Chapters	The BRISQ guidelines are proposed as an important and timely resource tool to strengthen communication and publications around biospecimen-related research and help reassure patient contributors and the advocacy community that the contributions are valued and respected. They make recommendations for the reporting of data elements for human biospecimens, defined as solid tissues and bodily fluids, used in biomedical studies. (Not included are cell lines, biospecimen derivatives such as DNA/RNA, proteins etc.)				

SPREC - Standard PReanalytical Code (sample treatment codes)

Source, year of publication	ISBER, 2012				
Sample types addressed	Human				
Link	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29377712/				
Content addressed	Pre-analytics & QM	Analysis	Data issues	Ethics/legal issues	Other bio-bank issues
	✓	-	✓	-	-
About the source (editors or authors)	The Standard Preanalytical Code for Biospecimens (SPREC) was first developed and published by the International Society for Biological and Environmental Repositories (ISBER) Biospecimen Science Working Group in 2009 and was updated in 2012.				
About the guideline/best practice document	The Standard Preanalytical Code for Biospecimens (SPREC) is a 7-digit code that describes the treatment of a sample before it is stored in a biobank. It aims to facilitate documentation and communication of the most important pre-analytical quality parameters of different types of biospecimens used for research. Pre-analytical variables such as standing time, centrifugation duration and intervals at a certain temperature, tissue removal procedure, etc. determine the quality of biosamples, which in turn is of great importance for the validity of the research results achieved with it.				
Chapters	<p>Fluid samples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of sample • Type of collection • Type of primary container • Pre-centrifugation (delay between collection and processing) • Centrifugation • Second centrifugation • Post-centrifugation delay • Long-term storage <p>Solid samples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of sample • Type of collection • Warm ischemia time • Cold ischemia time • Fixation/stabilization type • Fixation time • Long-term storage 				

5.3 Inventory of international ISO standards identified

The list below shows all ISO standards that were identified as “hits related to the topic” (as described in Table 2). They included both the standards of high and medium to low relevance.

Reference	Document Title	Topic/ Content	Owning Committee
Relevance high (H)			
ISO 20397-1	Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing — Part 1: Nucleic acid and library preparation	Analysis	ISO/TC 276
ISO 20397-2	Biotechnology — Massively parallel sequencing — Part 2: Quality evaluation of sequencing data	Analysis	ISO/TC 276
ISO 20397-3	Biotechnology -- Massively parallel sequencing -- Part 3: General requirements and guidance for metagenomics	Analysis	ISO/TC 276
ISO 20387:2018	General requirements for biobanking	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO 21899:2020	Biotechnology — Biobanking — General requirements for the validation and verification of processing methods for biological material in biobanks	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO 24088-1:2022	Biotechnology — Biobanking of microorganisms — Part 1: Bacteria and archaea	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO/AWI 20309	Biotechnology—Biobanking-Requirements for deep-sea biological materials	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TR 22758:2020	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Implementation guide for ISO 20387	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO 20691	Biotechnology - Requirements for data formatting and description in the life sciences	Data	ISO/TC 276
ISO 21710:2020	Biotechnology — Specification on data management and publication in microbial resource centers	Data	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TS 23494 -1:2023	Biotechnology – Provenance Information model for biological specimen and data — Part 1: Design concepts and general requirements	Data	ISO/TC 276
ISO 23494 -2	Biotechnology – Provenance Information model for biological specimen and data — Part 2: Common provenance model	Data	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TS 24420:2023	General Requirements for Data Processing of Shotgun Metagenomics	Data	ISO/TC 276
CEN/TS 17626:2021	Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA	Human	
ISO/AWI TS 18701	Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA	Human	ISO/TC 212
ISO/TS 23105:2021	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for the biobanking of plant biological material for research and development	Plant	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TS 23105:2021	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for the biobanking of plant biological material for research and development	Plant	ISO/TC 276
ISO 11063:2020	Soil quality — Direct extraction of soil DNA	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4

Relevance high (H) (continued)			
ISO 15903:2002	Soil quality — Format for recording soil and site information	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO 18400-101:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 101: Framework for the preparation and application of a sampling plan	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-102:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 102: Selection and application of sampling techniques	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-105:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-107:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 107: Recording and reporting	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-206:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 206: Collection, handling and storage of soil under aerobic conditions for the assessment of microbiological processes, biomass and diversity in the laboratory	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 18512:2007	Soil quality — Guidance on long and short term storage of soil samples	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 3
ISO/AWI 18400-105	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 105: Packaging, transport, storage and preservation of samples	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-106:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 106: Quality control and quality assurance	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
Relevance medium to low (M, L)			
ISO/TS 20388:2021	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for animal biological material	Animals	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TR 19838:2016	Microbiology — Cosmetics — Guidelines for the application of ISO standards on Cosmetic Microbiology	Cosmetic	
ISO 3985:2021	ISO TR 3985:2021 Biotechnology - Data Publication - Preliminary Considerations and Concepts	Data	ISO/TC 276
ISO 8000 family	Data quality	Data	ISO/TC 184
ISO 19444-1:2019	Document management — XML Forms Data Format — Part 1: Use of ISO 32000-2 (XFDX 3.0)	Data	ISO/TC 171/SC 2
ISO/DIS 19847	Ships and marine technology — Shipboard data servers to share field data at sea	Data, marine	ISO/TC 8/SC 6
ISO 8689-1:2000	Water quality — Biological classification of rivers — Part 1: Guidance on the interpretation of biological quality data from surveys of benthic macroinvertebrates	Data, water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 8689-2:2000	Water quality — Biological classification of rivers — Part 2: Guidance on the presentation of biological quality data from surveys of benthic macroinvertebrates	Data, water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 10272-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for detection and enumeration of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 10272-1:2017/Amd 1:2023	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for detection and enumeration of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection method — Amendment 1: Inclusion of methods for molecular confirmation and identification of thermotolerant	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 10272-2:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for detection and enumeration of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. — Part 2: Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 10272-2:2017/Amd 1:2023	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for detection and enumeration of <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. — Part 2: Colony-count technique — Amendment 1: Inclusion of methods for molecular confirmation and identification of thermotolerant <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. and changes in the performance testing of culture media	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 10273:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection of pathogenic <i>Yersinia enterocolitica</i>	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11133:2014	Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11133:2014/ Amd 1:2018	Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media — Amendment 1	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11133:2014/ Amd 2:2020	Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media — Amendment 2	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11290-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and of <i>Listeria</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11290-2:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> and of <i>Listeria</i> spp. — Part 2: Enumeration method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 13307:2013	Microbiology of food and animal feed — Primary production stage — Sampling techniques	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 14461-1:2005	Milk and milk products — Quality control in microbiological laboratories — Part 1: Analyst performance assessment for colony counts	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO 14461-2:2005	Milk and milk products — Quality control in microbiological laboratories — Part 2: Determination of the reliability of colony counts of parallel plates and subsequent dilution steps	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO 15213-1:2023	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of <i>Clostridium</i> spp. — Part 1: Enumeration of sulfite-reducing <i>Clostridium</i> spp. by colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 15214:1998	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of mesophilic lactic acid bacteria — Colony-count technique at 30 degrees C	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 15216-1/2017 - Amd 1:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 1: Method for quantification — Amendment 1	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 15216-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 1: Method for quantification	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 15216-2:2019	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR — Part 2: Method for detection	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 16649-1:2018	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive Escherichia coli — Part 1: Colony-count technique at 44 degrees C using membranes and 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl beta-D-glucuronide	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16649-2:2001	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive Escherichia coli — Part 2: Colony-count technique at 44 degrees C using 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl beta-D-glucuronide	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16649-3:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of beta-glucuronidase-positive Escherichia coli — Part 3: Detection and most probable number technique using 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl-β-D-glucuronide	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16654:2001	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of Escherichia coli O157	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16654:2001/Amd 1:2017	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of Escherichia coli O157 — Amendment 1: Annex B: Result of interlaboratory studies	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16654:2001/Amd 2:2023	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of Escherichia coli O157 — Amendment 2: Inclusion of performance testing of all culture media and reagents	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 17410:2019	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of psychrotrophic microorganisms	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 17604:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Carcass sampling for microbiological analysis	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 18593:2018	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal methods for surface sampling	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 19020:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the immunoenzymatic detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuffs	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21527-1:2008	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds — Part 1: Colony count technique in products with water activity greater than 0,95	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21527-2:2008	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds — Part 2: Colony count technique in products with water activity less than or equal to 0,95	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21528-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Enterobacteriaceae — Part 1: Detection of Enterobacteriaceae	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21528-2:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Enterobacteriaceae — Part 2: Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21567:2004	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of Shigella spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21871:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the determination of low numbers of presumptive Bacillus cereus — Most probable number technique and detection method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 21872-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the determination of <i>Vibrio</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection of potentially enteropathogenic <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> , <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> and <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 22964:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection of <i>Cronobacter</i> spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 23418:2022	Microbiology of the food chain — Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of bacteria — General requirements and guidance	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4831:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of coliforms — Most probable number technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4832:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coliforms — Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-1:2013	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 1: Colony count at 30 °C by the pour plate technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16654:2001/Amd 1:2017	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157 — Amendment 1: Annex B: Result of interlaboratory studies	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 16654:2001/Amd 2:2023	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157 — Amendment 2: Inclusion of performance testing of all culture media and reagents	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 17410:2019	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of psychrotrophic microorganisms	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 17604:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Carcass sampling for microbiological analysis	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 18593:2018	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal methods for surface sampling	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 19020:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the immunoenzymatic detection of staphylococcal enterotoxins in foodstuffs	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21527-1:2008	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds — Part 1: Colony count technique in products with water activity greater than 0,95	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21527-2:2008	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds — Part 2: Colony count technique in products with water activity less than or equal to 0,95	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21528-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Enterobacteriaceae — Part 1: Detection of Enterobacteriaceae	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21528-2:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Enterobacteriaceae — Part 2: Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21567:2004	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection of <i>Shigella</i> spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 21871:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the determination of low numbers of presumptive <i>Bacillus cereus</i> — Most probable number technique and detection method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 21872-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the determination of <i>Vibrio</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection of potentially enteropathogenic <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> , <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> and <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 22964:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection of <i>Cronobacter</i> spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 23418:2022	Microbiology of the food chain — Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of bacteria — General requirements and guidance	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4831:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of coliforms — Most probable number technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4832:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coliforms — Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-1:2013	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 1: Colony count at 30 °C by the pour plate technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-1:2013/Amd 1:2022	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 1: Colony count at 30 °C by the pour plate technique — Amendment 1: Clarification of scope	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-2:2013	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 2: Colony count at 30 °C by the surface plating technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-2:2013/Amd 1:2022	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 2: Colony count at 30 °C by the surface plating technique — Amendment 1: Clarification of scope	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 4833-2:2013/Cor 1:2014	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of microorganisms — Part 2: Colony count at 30 °C by the surface plating technique — Technical Corrigendum 1	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6579-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of <i>Salmonella</i> — Part 1: Detection of <i>Salmonella</i> spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6579-1:2017/Amd 1:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of <i>Salmonella</i> — Part 1: Detection of <i>Salmonella</i> spp. — Amendment 1: Broader range of incubation temperatures, amendment to the status of Annex D, and correction of the composition of MSRV and SC	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-1:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 1: General rules for the preparation of the initial suspension and decimal dilutions	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 6887-1:2017/CD Amd 1	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 1: General rules for the preparation of the initial suspension and decimal dilutions — Amendment 1: Requirements and guidance on the use of larger test portion size for qualitative methods	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-2:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 2: Specific rules for the preparation of meat and meat products	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-3:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-3:2017/Amd 1:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 3: Specific rules for the preparation of fish and fishery products — Amendment 1: Sample preparation for raw marine gastropods	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-4:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 4: Specific rules for the preparation of miscellaneous products	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6887-5:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 5: Specific rules for the preparation of milk and milk products	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6888-1:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and other species) — Part 1: Method using Baird-Parker agar medium	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6888-2:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and other species) — Part 2: Method using rabbit plasma fibrinogen agar medium	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 6888-3:2003	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and other species) — Part 3: Detection and MPN technique for low numbers	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 7251:2005	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of presumptive <i>Escherichia coli</i> — Most probable number technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 7932:2004	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of presumptive <i>Bacillus cereus</i> — Colony-count technique at 30 degrees C	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 7937:2004	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of <i>Clostridium perfringens</i> — Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO/TS 17728:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Sampling techniques for microbiological analysis of food and feed samples	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC9
ISO 11737-1:2018	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 1: Determination of a population of microorganisms on products	Other	ISO/TC 198

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 11737-1:2018/Amd 1:2021	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 1: Determination of a population of microorganisms on products — Amendment 1	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO 11737-2:2019	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 2: Tests of sterility performed in the definition, validation and maintenance of a sterilization process	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO 10381-6:2009	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 6: Guidance on the collection, handling and storage of soil under aerobic conditions for the assessment of microbiological processes, biomass and diversity in the laboratory	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 14240-1:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 1: Substrate-induced respiration method	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 14240-2:1997	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial biomass — Part 2: Fumigation-extraction method	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 14688-1:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Identification and classification of soil — Part 1: Identification and description	Soil	ISO/TC 182
ISO 14688-2:2017	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Identification and classification of soil — Part 2: Principles for a classification	Soil	ISO/TC 182
ISO 16720:2005	Soil quality — Pretreatment of samples by freeze-drying for subsequent analysis	soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 3
ISO 17155:2012	Soil quality — Determination of abundance and activity of soil microflora using respiration curves	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 17601:2016	Soil quality — Estimation of abundance of selected microbial gene sequences by quantitative PCR from DNA directly extracted from soil	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 17616:2019	Soil quality — Guidance on the choice and evaluation of bioassays for ecotoxicological characterization of soils and soil materials	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 18400-100:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 100: Guidance on the selection of sampling standards	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-103:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 103: Safety	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-104:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 104: Strategies	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-204:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 204: Guidance on sampling of soil gas	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-205:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 205: Guidance on the procedure for investigation of natural, near-natural and cultivated sites	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 22475-1:2021	Geotechnical investigation and testing — Sampling methods and groundwater measurements — Part 1: Technical principles for the sampling of soil, rock and groundwater	Soil	ISO/TC 182
ISO 23909:2008	Soil quality — Preparation of laboratory samples from large samples	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 3
ISO 28258:2013	Soil quality — Digital exchange of soil-related data	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO 28258:2013/ Amd 1:2019	Soil quality — Digital exchange of soil-related data — Amendment 1	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO/TS 10832:2009	Soil quality — Effects of pollutants on mycorrhizal fungi — Spore germination test	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 24480	ISO/PWI 24480 Biotechnology - Validation of database used for nucleic acid sequence validation	Validation	ISO/TC 276
ISO 15522:1999	Water quality — Determination of the inhibitory effect of water constituents on the growth of activated sludge microorganisms	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 16665:2014	Water quality — Guidelines for quantitative sampling and sample processing of marine soft-bottom macrofauna	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 16665:2014	Water quality — Guidelines for quantitative sampling and sample processing of marine soft-bottom macrofauna	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 19458:2006	Water quality — Sampling for microbiological analysis	Water	
ISO 5667-19:2004	Water quality — Sampling — Part 19: Guidance on sampling of marine sediments	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 6
ISO 8199:2018	Water quality — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations by culture	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO/AWI TS 16099	Water quality — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of microorganisms — Quality control and validation of molecular methods	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO/CD 24480	Biotechnology -- Validation of Database used for nucleotide sequence evaluation	Water	ISO/TC 276
ISO/CD 16000-43	Indoor air — Part 43: Standard method for assessing the reduction rate of culturable airborne fungi by air purifiers using a test chamber	Air	ISO/TC 146/SC 6
ISO/PWI 17597	Test Method for Airborne Microorganisms Filtration Efficiency (AMFE) and Decontamination Efficiency (AMDE) of Air-Cleaning Devices	Air	ISO/TC 142
ISO/TS 21569-7:2022	Horizontal methods for molecular biomarker analysis — Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products — Part 7: Real-time PCR based methods for the detection of CaMV and Agrobacterium Ti-plasmid derived DNA sequences	Analysis	ISO/TC 34/SC 16
ISO 21709:2020	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Process and quality requirements for establishment, maintenance and characterization of mammalian cell lines	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO 21709:2020/Amd 1:2021	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Process and quality requirements for establishment, maintenance and characterization of mammalian cell lines — Amendment 1	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO/CD 18209-1	Biotechnology — Biobanking of parasites — Part 1: Helminths	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO/WD 20070	Biotechnology — Biobanking — Requirements for sample containers for storing biological materials in biobanks	Biobanking	ISO/TC 276
ISO 11930:2019	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Evaluation of the antimicrobial protection of a cosmetic product	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217
ISO 11930:2019/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Evaluation of the antimicrobial protection of a cosmetic product — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217
ISO 16212:2017	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Enumeration of yeast and mould	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217
ISO 16212:2017/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Enumeration of yeast and mould — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)				
ISO 18415:2017	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of specified and non-specified microorganisms	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 18415:2017/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of specified and non-specified microorganisms — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 18416:2015	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Candida albicans</i>	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 18416:2015/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Candida albicans</i> — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21148:2017	Cosmetics — Microbiology — General instructions for microbiological examination	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21149:2017	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Enumeration and detection of aerobic mesophilic bacteria	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21149:2017/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Enumeration and detection of aerobic mesophilic bacteria — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21150:2015	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21150:2015/Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Escherichia coli</i> — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 21322:2020	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Testing of impregnated or coated wipes and masks	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 22717:2015	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 22717:2015/ Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 22718:2015	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 22718:2015/ Amd 1:2022	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Detection of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> — Amendment 1	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
ISO 29621:2017	Cosmetics — Microbiology — Guidelines for the risk assessment and identification of microbiologically low-risk products	Cosmetic	ISO/TC 217	
https://www.iso.org/standard/71276.html	Information technology — Big data reference architecture — Part 2: Use cases and derived requirements	Data	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42	
ISO 13307:2013	Microbiology of food and animal feed — Primary production stage — Sampling techniques	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9	
ISO 13559:2002	Butter, fermented milks and fresh cheese — Enumeration of contaminating microorganisms — Colony-count technique at 30 degrees C	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5	
ISO 16140-1:2016	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 1: Vocabulary	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9	
ISO 16140-2:2016	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 2: Protocol for the validation of alternative (proprietary) methods against a reference method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9	
ISO 16140-2:2016/CD Amd 1	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 2: Protocol for the validation of alternative (proprietary) methods against a reference method — Amendment 1	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9	
ISO 16140-3:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 3: Protocol for the verification of reference methods and validated alternative methods in a single laboratory	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9	

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 16140-4:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 4: Protocol for method validation in a single laboratory	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 16140-4:2020/CD Amd 1	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 4: Protocol for method validation in a single laboratory — Amendment 1: Annex H - Validation of larger test portion size for qualitative methods	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 16140-5:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 5: Protocol for factorial interlaboratory validation for non-proprietary methods	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 16140-6:2019	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 6: Protocol for the validation of alternative (proprietary) methods for microbiological confirmation and typing procedures	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 17468:2016	Microbiology of the food chain — Technical requirements and guidance on establishment or revision of a standardized reference method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 18465:2017	Microbiology of the food chain — Quantitative determination of emetic toxin (cereulide) using LC-MS/MS	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 18743:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection of Trichinella larvae in meat by artificial digestion method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 18743:2015/D Amd 1	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection of Trichinella larvae in meat by artificial digestion method — Amendment 1: Revision of text and minor technical issues, references update, and inclusion of performance characteristics of the method by interlaboratory study	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 18744:2016	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection and enumeration of Cryptosporidium and Giardia in fresh leafy green vegetables and berry fruits	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 20836:2021	Microbiology of the food chain — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of microorganisms — Thermal performance testing of thermal cyclers	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 20837:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Requirements for sample preparation for qualitative detection	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 20838:2006	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Requirements for amplification and detection for qualitative methods	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 20976-1:2019	Microbiology of the food chain — Requirements and guidelines for conducting challenge tests of food and feed products — Part 1: Challenge tests to study growth potential, lag time and maximum growth rate	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 20976-2:2022	Microbiology of the food chain — Requirements and guidelines for conducting challenge tests of food and feed products — Part 2: Challenge tests to study inactivation potential and kinetic parameters	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 21187:2021	Milk — Quantitative determination of microbiological quality — Guidance for establishing and verifying a conversion relationship between results of an alternative method and anchor method results	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
<u>ISO 21872-1:2017/Amd 1</u>	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the determination of <i>Vibrio</i> spp. — Part 1: Detection of potentially enteropathogenic <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> , <i>Vibrio cholerae</i> and <i>Vibrio vulnificus</i> — Amendment 1: Inclusion of performance testing of culture media and reagents	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 22117:2019</u>	Microbiology of the food chain — Specific requirements and guidance for proficiency testing by interlaboratory comparison	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 22118:2011</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of food-borne pathogens — Performance characteristics	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 22119:2011</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — General requirements and definitions	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 22174:2005</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — General requirements and definitions	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 23418:2022</u>	Microbiology of the food chain — Whole genome sequencing for typing and genomic characterization of bacteria — General requirements and guidance	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 6887-6:2013</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feed — Preparation of test samples, initial suspension and decimal dilutions for microbiological examination — Part 6: Specific rules for the preparation of samples taken at the primary production stage	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 6888-1:2021/DAmD 1</u>	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and other species) — Part 1: Method using Baird-Parker agar medium — Amendment 1: Corrections	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 6888-2:2021/DAmD 1</u>	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of coagulase-positive staphylococci (<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and other species) — Part 2: Method using rabbit plasma fibrinogen agar medium — Amendment 1: Corrections	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 7218:2007</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 7218:2007/Amd 1:2013</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations — Amendment 1	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 7251:2005/DAmD 1</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of presumptive <i>Escherichia coli</i> — Most probable number technique — Amendment 1: Inclusion of performance testing of culture media and reagents	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
<u>ISO 7889:2003</u>	Yogurt — Enumeration of characteristic microorganisms — Colony-count technique at 37 degrees C	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
<u>ISO 7932:2004/Amd 1:2020</u>	Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs — Horizontal method for the enumeration of presumptive <i>Bacillus cereus</i> — Colony-count technique at 30 degrees C — Amendment 1: Inclusion of optional tests	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 8553:2004	Milk — Enumeration of microorganisms — Plate-loop technique at 30 degrees C	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO 9232:2003	Yogurt — Identification of characteristic microorganisms (Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. bulgaricus and Streptococcus thermophilus)	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO 9232:2003/DAmD 1	Yogurt — Identification of characteristic microorganisms (Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. bulgaricus and Streptococcus thermophilus) — Amendment 1: Inclusion of performance testing of culture media and reagents	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO/AWI 11133	Microbiology of food, animal feed and water — Preparation, production, storage and performance testing of culture media	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/AWI 21527	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the enumeration of yeasts and moulds	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/AWI 21722	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for enumeration of enterococci	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/AWI 23691	Microbiology of the food chain — Determination and use of cardinal values	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/AWI 9811	Microbiology of the food chain — Molecular detection of Cyclospora cayetanensis in fresh produce using real-time PCR	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD 13136-1	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection, isolation and characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) — Part 1: Horizontal method for the detection and isolation of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC)	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD 13136-2	Microbiology of the food chain — Detection, isolation and characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) — Part 2: Horizontal method for the characterization of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) isolates	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD 16140-7	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 7: Protocol for validation of identification methods of microorganisms	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD 16140-7	Microbiology of the food chain — Method validation — Part 7: Protocol for validation of identification methods of microorganisms	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD 7889	Yogurt — Enumeration of characteristic microorganisms — Colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 5
ISO/CD TS 15213-3	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Clostridium spp. — Part 3: Detection of Clostridium perfringens	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/CD TS 6579-4	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 4: Identification of monophasic Salmonella Typhimurium (1,4,[5],12:i:-) by polymerase chain reaction (PCR)	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/DIS 15213-2	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection and enumeration of Clostridium spp. — Part 2: Enumeration of Clostridium perfringens by colony-count technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO/DIS 17468	Microbiology of the food chain — Technical requirements and guidance on establishment or revision of a standardized reference method	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/DIS 22174	Microbiology of the food chain — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection and quantification of microorganisms — General requirements and definitions	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/DIS 7218	Microbiology of the food chain — General requirements and guidance for microbiological examinations	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TR 6579-3:2014	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 3: Guidelines for serotyping of Salmonella spp.	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TS 13136:2012	Microbiology of food and animal feed — Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based method for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Horizontal method for the detection of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) and the determination of O157, O111, O26, O103 and O145 serogroups	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TS 17919:2013	Microbiology of the food chain — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Detection of botulinum type A, B, E and F neurotoxin-producing clostridia	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TS 18867:2015	Microbiology of the food chain — Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens — Detection of pathogenic Yersinia enterocolitica and Yersinia pseudotuberculosis	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TS 21872-2:2020	Microbiology of the food chain — Horizontal method for the determination of Vibrio spp. — Part 2: Enumeration of total and potentially enteropathogenic Vibrio parahaemolyticus in seafood using nucleic acid hybridization	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO/TS 6579-2:2012	Microbiology of food and animal feed — Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella — Part 2: Enumeration by a miniaturized most probable number technique	Food	ISO/TC 34/SC 9
ISO 11737-1:2018	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 1: Determination of a population of microorganisms on products	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO 11737-1:2018/Amd 1:2021	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 1: Determination of a population of microorganisms on products — Amendment 1	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO 15714:2019	Method of evaluating the UV dose to airborne microorganisms transiting in-duct ultraviolet germicidal irradiation devices	Other	ISO/TC 142
ISO 16256:2021	Clinical laboratory testing and in vitro diagnostic test systems — Broth micro-dilution reference method for testing the in vitro activity of antimicrobial agents against yeast fungi involved in infectious diseases	Other	ISO/TC 212
ISO 17822:2020	In vitro diagnostic test systems — Nucleic acid amplification-based examination procedures for detection and identification of microbial pathogens — Laboratory quality practice guide	Other	ISO/TC 212
ISO 21703:2019	Surface active agents — Microbiology — Microbiological test methods for liquid hand dishwashing	Other	ISO/TC 91

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 22442-3:2007	Medical devices utilizing animal tissues and their derivatives — Part 3: Validation of the elimination and/or inactivation of viruses and transmissible spongiform encephalopathy (TSE) agents	Other	ISO/TC 194
ISO 22467:2021	Traditional Chinese medicine — Determination of microorganisms in natural products	Other	ISO/TC 249
ISO 22612:2005	Clothing for protection against infectious agents — Test method for resistance to dry microbial penetration	Other	ISO/TC 94/SC 13
ISO 24190	ISO/CD 24190 Biotechnology — Analytical methods — Risk-based approach for method selection and validation for rapid microbial detection in bioprocesses	Other	ISO/TC 276
ISO/CD 6674	Fertilizers, soil conditioners and beneficial substances — Microbiology- Detection of Staphylococcus aureus coagulase-positive	Other	ISO/TC 134
ISO/CD 6675	Fertilizers, soil conditioners and beneficial substances — Microbiology — Detection of Escherichia coli	Other	ISO/TC 134
ISO/FDIS 11737-3	Sterilization of health care products — Microbiological methods — Part 3: Bacterial endotoxin testing	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO/FDIS 24190	Biotechnology — Analytical methods — Risk-based approach for method selection and validation for rapid microbial detection in bioprocesses	Other	ISO/TC 276
ISO/TS 22456:2021	Sterilization of healthcare products — Microbiological methods— Guidance on conducting bioburden determinations and tests of sterility for biologics and tissue-based products	Other	ISO/TC 198
ISO 8784-1:2014	Pulp, paper and board — Microbiological examination — Part 1: Enumeration of bacteria and bacterial spores based on disintegration	Paper	ISO/TC 6/SC 2
ISO 8784-3:2022	Pulp, paper and board — Microbiological examination — Part 3: Enumeration of yeast and mould based on disintegration	Paper	ISO/TC 6/SC 2
ISO/FDIS 8784-2	Pulp, paper and board — Microbiological examination — Part 2: Enumeration of bacteria, yeast and mould on surface	Paper	ISO/TC 6/SC 2
ISO 846:2019	Plastics — Evaluation of the action of microorganisms	Plastics	ISO/TC 61/SC 6
ISO/CD 846	Plastics — Evaluation of the action of microorganisms	Plastics	ISO/TC 61/SC 6
ISO 1237:1981	Mustard seed — Specification	Seeds	ISO/TC 34/SC 7
ISO 3760:2002	Oil of celery seed (Apium graveolens L.)	Seeds	ISO/TC 54
ISO 4254-9:2018	Agricultural machinery — Safety — Part 9: Seed drills	Seeds	ISO/TC 23/SC 3
ISO 5061:2002	Animal feeding stuffs — Determination of castor oil seed husks — Microscope method	Seeds	ISO/TC 34/SC 10
ISO 6574:1986	Celery seed (Apium graveolens Linnaeus) — Specification	Seeds	ISO/TC 34/SC 7
ISO 7256-1:1984	Sowing equipment — Test methods — Part 1: Single seed drills (precision drills)	Seeds	ISO/TC 23
ISO 7256-2:1984	Sowing equipment — Test methods — Part 2: Seed drills for sowing in lines	Seeds	ISO/TC 23

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 7927-1:2023	Spices and condiments — Fennel seed, whole or ground — Part 1: Bitter fennel seed specification (<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> P. Miller var. <i>vulgare</i>)	Seeds	ISO/TC 34/SC 7
ISO 7927-2:2023	Spices and condiments — Fennel seed, whole or ground — Part 2: Sweet fennel seed specification (<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> var. <i>panmorium</i>)	Seeds	ISO/TC 34/SC 7
ISO 9301:2003	Oil of cumin seed (<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L.)	Seeds	ISO/TC 54
ISO/DIS 23016-4	Fine bubble technology — Agricultural applications — Part 4: Test method for evaluating the number concentration of ultrafine bubbles (UFB) achieving the promotion of barley seed germination	Seeds	ISO/TC 281
ISO/NP 20196	Hemp seed oil — Determination of five cannabinoids by high performance liquid chromatography with ultraviolet detection (HPLC-UV)	seeds	ISO/TC 34
ISO/PWI 8961	Traditional Chinese Medicine--Areca catechu seed	Seeds	ISO/TC 249
ISO 11267:2014	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of <i>Collembola</i> (<i>Folsomia candida</i>) by soil contaminants	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 11269-1:2012	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Part 1: Method for the measurement of inhibition of root growth	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 11269-2:2012	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Part 2: Effects of contaminated soil on the emergence and early growth of higher plants	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 14238:2012	Soil quality — Biological methods — Determination of nitrogen mineralization and nitrification in soils and the influence of chemicals on these processes	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 14254:2018	Soil quality — Determination of exchangeable acidity using barium chloride solution as extractant	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 3
ISO 14507:2003	Soil quality — Pretreatment of samples for determination of organic contaminants	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 3
ISO 15685:2012	Soil quality — Determination of potential nitrification and inhibition of nitrification — Rapid test by ammonium oxidation	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 15799:2019	Soil quality — Guidance on the ecotoxicological characterization of soils and soil materials	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 15800:2019	Soil quality — Characterization of soil with respect to human exposure	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 16072:2002	Soil quality — Laboratory methods for determination of microbial soil respiration	Soil	
ISO 16387:2014	Soil quality — Effects of contaminants on <i>Enchytraeidae</i> (<i>Enchytraeus</i> sp.) — Determination of effects on reproduction	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 17126:2005	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Screening test for emergence of lettuce seedlings (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.)	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 17924:2018	Soil quality — Assessment of human exposure from ingestion of soil and soil material — Procedure for the estimation of the human bioaccessibility/bioavailability of metals in soil	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO 18187:2016	Soil quality — Contact test for solid samples using the dehydrogenase activity of <i>Arthrobacter globiformis</i>	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 18311:2016	Soil quality — Method for testing effects of soil contaminants on the feeding activity of soil dwelling organisms — Bait-lamina test	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 18400-201:2017	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 201: Physical pretreatment in the field	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-202:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 202: Preliminary investigations	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 18400-203:2018	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 203: Investigation of potentially contaminated sites	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7
ISO 20130:2018	Soil quality — Measurement of enzyme activity patterns in soil samples using colorimetric substrates in micro-well plates	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 21285:2019	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of the soil mite (<i>Hypoaspis aculeifer</i>) by soil contaminants	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 21479:2019	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Leaf fatty acid composition of plants used to assess soil quality	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 23753-1:2019	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 1: Method using triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC)	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 23753-1:2019/Amd 1:2020	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 1: Method using triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) — Amendment 1	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 23753-2:2019	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 2: Method using iodotetrazolium chloride (INT)	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 23753-2:2019/Amd 1:2020	Soil quality — Determination of dehydrogenases activity in soils — Part 2: Method using iodotetrazolium chloride (INT) — Amendment 1	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 23992:2022	Soil quality — Framework for detailed recording and monitoring of changes in dynamic soil properties	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO/AWI 18718	Assessment of soil functions and related-ecosystem services: definitions and conceptual Framework	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO/AWI 18721	Assessment of ecological soil functions: indicators and methods	Soil	ISO/TC 190
ISO/CD 17126	Soil quality — Determination of the effects of pollutants on soil flora — Screening test for emergence of lettuce seedlings (<i>Lactuca sativa</i> L.)	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/CD 18187	Soil quality — Contact test for solid samples using the dehydrogenase activity of <i>Arthrobacter globiformis</i>	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/CD 23611-2	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 2: Sampling and extraction of micro-arthropods (<i>Collembola</i> and <i>Acarina</i>)	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/CD 23611-5	Soil quality — Sampling of soil invertebrates — Part 5: Sampling and extraction of soil macro-invertebrates	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/DIS 11267	Soil quality — Inhibition of reproduction of <i>Collembola</i> (<i>Folsomia candida</i>) by soil contaminants	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/DIS 18400-301	Soil quality — Sampling — Part 301: Sampling- and on site semi-quantitative determinations of volatiles in field investigations	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 7

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)			
ISO/FDIS 16387	Soil quality — Effects of contaminants on Enchytraeidae (Enchytraeus sp.) — Determination of effects on reproduction	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/TS 29843-1:2010	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial diversity — Part 1: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) and phospholipid ether lipids (PLEL) analysis	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO/TS 29843-2:2021	Soil quality — Determination of soil microbial diversity — Part 2: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) using the simple PLFA extraction method	Soil	ISO/TC 190/SC 4
ISO 11721-1:2001	Textiles — Determination of resistance of cellulose-containing textiles to micro-organisms — Soil burial test — Part 1: Assessment of rot-retardant finishing	Textile	ISO/TC 38
ISO 11721-2:2003	Textiles — Determination of the resistance of cellulose-containing textiles to micro-organisms — Soil burial test — Part 2: Identification of long-term resistance of a rot retardant finish	Textile	ISO/TC 38
ISO 10253:2016	Water quality — Marine algal growth inhibition test with Skeletonema sp. and Phaeodactylum tricornutum	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 10710:2010	Water quality — Growth inhibition test with the marine and brackish water macroalga Ceramium tenuicorne	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 13843:2017	Water quality — Requirements for establishing performance characteristics of quantitative microbiological methods	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO 29201:2012	Water quality — The variability of test results and the uncertainty of measurement of microbiological enumeration methods	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO 5667-9:1992	Water quality — Sampling — Part 9: Guidance on sampling from marine waters	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 6
ISO 7704:2023	Water quality — Requirements for the performance testing of membrane filters used for direct enumeration of microorganisms by culture methods	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO 9509:2006	Water quality — Toxicity test for assessing the inhibition of nitrification of activated sludge microorganisms	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO/CD 13647	Water quality — Enumeration of culturable microorganisms — Colony count by spread plate inoculation on R2A medium	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 4
ISO/DIS 10253	Water quality — Marine algal growth inhibition test with Skeletonema sp. and Phaeodactylum tricornutum	Water	ISO/TC 147/SC 5
ISO 10872:2020	Water and soil quality — Determination of the toxic effect of sediment and soil samples on growth, fertility and reproduction of Caenorhabditis elegans (Nematoda)	Water, Soil	ISO/TC 147/SC 5

5.4 Inventory of European CEN standards identified

The list below shows all CEN standards that MUG identified as “hits related to the topic” (as described in Table 2). They included both the standards of high and medium to low relevance.

Reference	Document Title	Topic/ Content
Relevance high (H)		
CEN/TS 17626:2021	Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations — Specifications for pre-examination processes for human specimens — Isolated microbiome DNA	Human
CEN/TS 17708:2022	Plant biostimulants - Preparation of sample for microbial analysis	Plant
Relevance medium to low (M, L)		
CEN/TR 15175:2006	Characterization of sludges - Protocol for organizing and conducting inter-laboratory tests of methods for chemical and microbiological analysis of sludges	QC
CEN ISO/TS 17728:2015	Microbiology of the food chain - Sampling techniques for microbiological analysis of food and feed samples (ISO/TS 17728:2015)	Food
CEN/TS 17714:2022	Plant biostimulants - Determination of microorganisms' concentration	Plant
CEN/TS 15568:2006	Foodstuffs - Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products - Sampling strategies	Food
CEN ISO/TS 29843-1:2014	Soil quality - Determination of soil microbial diversity - Part 1: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) and phospholipid ether lipids (PLEL) analysis (ISO/TS 29843-1:2010)	Soil
CEN ISO/TS 6579-2:2012	Microbiology of food and animal feed - Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella - Part 2: Enumeration by a miniaturized most probable number technique (ISO/TS 6579-2:2012)	Food
CEN ISO/TS 13136:2012	Microbiology of food and animal feed - Real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based method for the detection of food-borne pathogens - Horizontal method for the detection of Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) and the determination of O157, O111, O26, O103 and O145 serogroups (ISO/TS 13136:2012)	Food
CEN ISO/TR 6579-3:2014	Microbiology of the food chain - Horizontal method for the detection, enumeration and serotyping of Salmonella - Part 3: Guidelines for serotyping of Salmonella spp. (ISO/TR 6579-3:2014)	Food
CEN/TS 16115-2:2016	Ambient air - Measurement of bioaerosols - Part 2: Planning and evaluation of plant-related plume measurements	Others
CEN ISO/TR 20342-7:2022	Assistive products for tissue integrity when lying down - Part 7: Foam properties, characteristics and performance (ISO/TR 20342-7:2021)	Others
CEN ISO/TS 23758:2021	Guidelines for the validation of qualitative screening methods for the detection of residues of veterinary drugs in milk and milk products (ISO/TS 23758:2021)	Food
CEN ISO/TR 19838:2016	Microbiology - Cosmetics - Guidelines for the application of ISO standards on Cosmetic Microbiology (ISO/TR 19838:2016)	Cosmetics
CEN ISO/TS 17919:2013	Microbiology of the food chain - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of <i>food-borne pathogens</i> - Detection of botulinum type A, B, E and F neurotoxin-producing clostridia (ISO/TS 17919:2013)	Food
CEN ISO/TS 18867:2015	Microbiology of the <i>food chain</i> - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) for the detection of food-borne pathogens - Detection of pathogenic Yersinia enterocolitica and Yersinia pseudotuberculosis (ISO/DTS 18867:2015)	Food

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)		
CEN/TS 17811:2022	Molecular in vitro diagnostic examinations - Specifications for pre-examination processes for urine and other body fluids - Isolated cell free DNA	Human
CEN/TR 15367-1:2020	Petroleum products - Guidelines for good housekeeping - Part 1: Automotive diesel fuels	Others
CEN ISO/TS 29843-2:2021	Soil quality - Determination of soil microbial diversity - Part 2: Method by phospholipid fatty acid analysis (PLFA) using the simple PLFA extraction method (ISO/TS 29843-2:2021)	Soil
CEN ISO/TR 24475:2013	Cosmetics - Good Manufacturing Practices - General training document (ISO/TR 24475:2010)	Cosmetics
CEN ISO/TR 26369:2009	Cosmetics - Sun protection test methods - Review and evaluation of methods to assess the photoprotection of sun protection products (ISO/TR 26369:2009)	Cosmetics
CEN ISO/TS 21623:2018	Workplace exposure - Assessment of dermal exposure to nano-objects and their aggregates and agglomerates (NOAA) (ISO/TS 21623:2017)	Cosmetics
CEN/TR 15371-2:2021	Safety of toys - Interpretations - Part 2: Replies to requests for interpretation of the chemical standards in the EN 71-series	Cosmetics
CEN/TR 17559:2022	Algae and algae products - Food and feed applications: General overview of limits, procedures and analytical methods	Cosmetics
CEN/TR 17611:2021	Algae and algae products - Specifications for cosmetic sector applications	Cosmetics
CEN/TS 16595:2013	CBRN - Vulnerability Assessment and Protection of People at Risk	Cosmetics
CEN/TS 17273:2018	Nanotechnologies - Guidance on detection and identification of nano-objects in complex matrices	Cosmetics
CEN Guide 16:2017	Guide for addressing chemicals in standards for consumer-relevant products	Food
CEN/TR 15298:2006	Foodstuffs - Sample comminution for mycotoxins analysis - Comparison between dry milling and slurry mixing	Food
CEN/TR 15356-1:2006	Validation and interpretation of analytical methods, migration testing and analytical data for materials and articles in contact with food - Part 1: General considerations	Food
CEN/TR 15569:2009	Solid biofuels - A guide for a quality assurance system	Food
CEN/TR 15584:2007	Characterisation of sludges - Guide to risk assessment especially in relation to use and disposal of sludges	Food
CEN/TR 15641:2007	Food analysis - Determination of pesticide residues by LC-MS/MS - Tandem mass spectrometric parameters	Food
CEN/TR 15645-1:2008	Paper and board intended to come into contact with foodstuffs - Calibration of the odour test - Part 1: Odour	Food
CEN/TR 15645-2:2008	Paper and board intended to come into contact with foodstuffs - Calibration of the off flavour test - Part 2: Fatty food	Food
CEN/TR 15645-2:2008/AC:2008	Paper and board intended to come into contact with foodstuffs - Calibration of the off-flavour test - Part 2: Fatty food	Food
CEN/TR 15645-3:2008	Paper and board intended to come into contact with foodstuffs - Calibration of the off-flavour test - Part 3: Dry food	Food
CEN/TR 16059:2010	Food analysis - Performance criteria for single laboratory validated methods of analysis for the determination of mycotoxins	Food
CEN/TR 16208:2011	Biobased products - Overview of standards	Food
CEN/TR 16338:2012	Foodstuffs - Detection of food allergens - Template for supplying information about immunological methods and molecular biological methods	Food

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)

CEN/TR 16468:2013	Food analysis - Determination of pesticide residues by GC-MS - Retention times, mass spectrometric parameters and detector response information	Food
CEN/TR 16699:2014	Foodstuffs - Determination of pesticide residues by GC-MS/MS - Tandem mass spectrometric parameters	Food
CEN/TR 17063:2017	Foods of plant origin - Multimethod for the determination of pesticide residues using GC- or LC-based analysis following acetonitrile extraction/partitioning and cleanup by dispersive SPE - Validation data of the modular QuEChERS-method	Food
CEN/TR 17612:2021	Algae and algae products - Specifications for pharmaceutical sector applications	Food
CEN/TS 13130-10:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 10: Determination of acrylamide in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-11:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 11: Determination of 11-aminoundecanoic acid in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-12:2005	Material and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 12: Determination of 1,3-benzenedimethanamine in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-13:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 13: Determination of 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane (Bisphenol A) in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-14:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 14: Determination of 3,3-bis(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-2-indoline in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-15:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 15: Determination of 1,3-butadiene in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-16:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 16: Determination of caprolactam and caprolactam salt in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-17:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 17: Determination of carbonyl chloride in plastics	Food
CEN/TS 13130-18:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 18: Determination of 1,2-dihydroxybenzene, 1,3-dihydroxybenzene, 1,4-dihydroxybenzene, 4,4'-dihydroxybenzophenone and 4,4'-dihydroxybiphenyl in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-19:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 19: Determination of dimethylaminoethanol in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-20:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 20: Determination of epichlorohydrin in plastics	Food
CEN/TS 13130-21:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 21: Determination of ethylenediamine and hexamethylenediamine in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-22:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 22: Determination of ethylene oxide and propylene oxide in plastics	Food
CEN/TS 13130-23:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 23: Determination of formaldehyde and hexamethylenetetramine in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-24:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 24: Determination of maleic acid and maleic anhydride in food simulants	Food

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)		
CEN/TS 13130-25:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 25: Determination of 4-methyl-1-pentene in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-26:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 26: Determination of 1-octene and tetrahydrofuran in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-27:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 27: Determination of 2,4,6-triamino-1,3,5-triazine in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-28:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 28: Determination of 1,1,1-trimethylolpropane in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 13130-9:2005	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics substances subject to limitation - Part 9: Determination of acetic acid, vinyl ester in food simulants	Food
CEN/TS 14234:2002	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Polymeric coatings on paper and board- Guide to the selection of conditions and test methods for overall migration	Food
CEN/TS 14235:2002	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Polymeric coatings on metal substrates - Guide to the selection of conditions and test methods for overall migration	Food
CEN/TS 14537:2003	Foodstuffs - Determination of neohesperidin-dihydrochalcon	Food
CEN/TS 14577:2003	Materials and articles in contact with foodstuffs - Plastics - Polymeric additives - Test method for the determination of the mass fraction of a polymeric additive that lies below 1000 Daltons	Food
CEN/TS 15606:2009	Foodstuffs - Determination of acesulfame-K, aspartame, neohesperidine-dihydrochalcone and saccharin - High performance liquid chromatographic method	Food
CEN/TS 15633-2:2013	Foodstuffs - Detection of food allergens by immunological methods - Part 2: Quantitative determination of hazelnut with an enzyme immunoassay using monoclonal antibodies and biconchonic acid-protein detection	Food
CEN/TS 15633-3:2012	Foodstuffs - Detection of food allergens by immunological methods - Part 3: Quantitative determination of hazelnut with an enzyme immunoassay using polyclonal antibodies and Lowry protein detection	Food
CEN/TS 16233-1:2011	Foodstuffs - HPLC method for the determination of xanthophylls in fish flesh - Part 1: Determination of astaxanthin and canthaxanthin	Food
CEN/TS 16233-2:2011	Foodstuffs - HPLC method for the determination of xanthophylls in fish flesh - Part 2: Identification of the enantiomer ratio of astaxanthin	Food
CEN/TS 16621:2014	Food analysis - Determination of benzo[a]pyrene, benz[a]anthracene, chrysene and benzo[b]fluoranthene in foodstuffs by high performance liquid chromatography with fluorescence detection (HPLC-FD)	Food
CEN/TS 16707:2014	Foodstuffs - Methods of analysis for the detection of genetically modified organisms and derived products - Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) based screening strategies	Food
CEN/TS 16731:2014	Foodstuffs - Determination of hydride-reactive arsenic compounds in rice by atomic absorption spectrometry (Hydride-AAS) following acid extraction	Food
CEN/TS 16861:2015	Plastics - Recycled plastics - Determination of selected marker compounds in food grade recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	Food
CEN/TS 17061:2019	Foodstuffs - Guidelines for the calibration and quantitative determination of pesticide residues and organic contaminants using chromatographic methods	Food
CEN/TS 17062:2019	Foods of plant origin - Multimethod for the determination of pesticide residues in vegetable oils by LC-MS/MS (QuOil)	Food

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)		
CEN/TS 17083:2017	Foodstuffs - Determination of acrylamide in food and coffee by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS)	Food
CEN/TS 17303:2019	Foodstuffs - DNA barcoding of fish and fish products using defined mitochondrial cytochrome b and cytochrome c oxidase I gene segments	Food
CEN/TS 17329-1:2021	Foodstuffs - General guidelines for the validation of qualitative real-time PCR methods - Part 1: Single-laboratory validation	Food
CEN/TS 17329-2:2019	Foodstuffs - General guidelines for the validation of qualitative real-time PCR methods - Part 2: Collaborative study	Food
CEN/TS 17497:2020	Pulp, paper and paperboard - Determination of bisphenol A in extracts from paper and paperboard	Food
CEN/TS 17630:2021	Pulp, paper and paperboard - Determination of anthraquinone in extracts from pulp, paper and paperboard	Food
CEN/TS 17743:2022	Foodstuff - Determination of pesticide residues by ethyl acetate extraction using GC- and LC-MS/MS (SweEt)	Food
CEN/TS 17780:2022	Organic, organo-mineral and inorganic fertilizers - Detection of Salmonella spp.	Food
CEN ISO/TR 20736:2023	Sludge recovery, recycling, treatment and disposal - Guidance on thermal treatment of sludge (ISO/TR 20736:2021)	Soil
CEN ISO/TS 16558-2:2015	Soil quality - Risk-based petroleum hydrocarbons - Part 2: Determination of aliphatic and aromatic fractions of semi-volatile petroleum hydrocarbons using gas chromatography with flame ionization detection (GC/FID) (ISO/TS 16558-2:2015)	Soil
CEN/TR 13097:2010	Characterization of sludges - Good practice for sludge utilisation in agriculture	Soil
CEN/TR 13983:2003	Characterization of sludges - Good practice for sludge utilisation in land reclamation	Soil
CEN/TR 15126:2005	Characterization of sludges - Good practice for landfilling of sludges and sludge treatment residues	Soil
CEN/TR 15214-1:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 1: Membrane filtration method for quantification	Soil
CEN/TR 15214-2:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 2: Miniaturised method (Most Probable Number) by inoculation in liquid medium	Soil
CEN/TR 15214-3:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 3: Macromethod (Most Probable Number) in liquid medium	Soil
CEN/TR 15215-1:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Salmonella spp. in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 1: Membrane filtration method for quantitative resuscitation of sub-lethally stressed bacteria (to confirm efficacy of log drop treatment procedures)	Soil
CEN/TR 15215-2:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Salmonella spp. in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 2: Liquid enrichment method in selenite-cystine medium followed by Rapport-Vassiliadis for semi-quantitative Most Probable Number (MPN) determination	Soil
CEN/TR 15215-3:2006	Characterization of sludges - Detection and enumeration of Salmonella spp. in sludges, soils, soil improvers, growing media and biowastes - Part 3: Presence/absence method by liquid enrichment in peptone-novobiocin medium followed by Rapport-Vassiliadis	Soil
CEN/TR 15463:2007	Characterization of sludges - Physical consistency - Thixotropic behaviour and piling behaviour	Soil

Relevance medium to low (M, L) (continued)

CEN/TR 16193:2013	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Detection and enumeration of Escherichia coli	Soil
CEN/TR 16788:2014	Characterization of sludges - Guideline of good practice for thermal processes	Soil
CEN/TS 13714:2013	Characterization of sludges - Sludge management in relation to use or disposal	Soil
CEN/TS 15937:2013	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of specific electrical conductivity	Soil
CEN/TS 16177:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Extraction for the determination of extractable ammonia, nitrate and nitrite	Soil
CEN/TS 16182:2012	Sludge treated biowaste and soil - Determination of nonylphenols (NP) and nonylphenol-mono- and diethoxylates using gas chromatography with mass selective detection (GC-MS)	Soil
CEN/TS 16183:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of selected phthalates using capillary gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GC-MS)	Soil
CEN/TS 16189:2012	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of linear alkylbenzene sulfonates (LAS) by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with fluorescence detection (FLD) or mass selective detection (MS)	Soil
CEN/TS 16201:2013	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of viable plant seeds and propagules	Soil
CEN/TS 16202:2013	Sludge, treated biowaste and soil - Determination of impurities and stones	Soil
CEN/TS 16375:2013	Liming materials - Determination of the amount of residual finely ground carbonate in soils - Volumetric method	Soil
CEN/TS 16637-1:2018	Construction products - Assessment of release of dangerous substances - Part 1: Guidance for the determination of leaching tests and additional testing steps	Soil
CEN/TS 16800:2020	Guideline for the validation of physico-chemical analytical methods	Soil
CEN/TS 17006:2016	Earthworks - Continuous Compaction Control (CCC)	Soil
CEN/TS 17700-5:2022	Plant biostimulants - Claims - Part 5: Determination of availability of confined nutrients in the soil or rhizosphere	Soil
CEN/TS 17725:2022	Plant biostimulants - Determination of the quantity (indicated by mass or volume)	Soil
CEN/TS 17728:2022	Organic soil improvers - Determination of specific parameters	Soil
CEN/TS 17729:2022	Soil improvers - Determination of specific parameters	Soil
CEN/TS 17732:2022	Soil improvers and growing media - Terminology	Soil
CEN/TS 17733:2022	Soil improvers and growing media - Sampling and sample preparation	Soil
CEN/TS 17883:2022	Environmental characterization of leachates from waste and soil using reproductive and toxicological gene expression in Daphnia magn	Soil

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